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Abstract	<p>As part of the European Data Strategy, the European Commission (EC) is working towards establishing a Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) that covers issues such as climate change, circular economy, pollution, biodiversity and deforestation. The EC recognises the increasing importance of including citizen-generated data into political decision-making and as such integrating citizen science data into the GDDS. To be fit for integration, citizen-generated data will need to comply to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) guiding principles. Research however shows that data sharing practices in citizen science projects are often inconsistent, presenting challenges for data interoperability and integration at larger scales.</p> <p>This document is the Deliverable 2.4 for the AD4GD project. It presents the results achieved in the context of Task 2.3 “Defined co-design methodologies for CitSci for Green Deal topics and facilitated convergence to a common semantics”. The document is a follow-up version of the Deliverable 2.3 “CitSci Data Interoperability Obstacles and Solutions” that presented the outcomes of Task 2.2 “Identification of CitSci data including complementary socioeconomic and INSPIRE data”.</p> <p>Task 2.2 aimed to investigate the state of play with citizen science data in regard to FAIR compliance by examining citizen science platforms, tools, and prominent initiatives. Building on the results, Task 2.3 focused on engaging with real-world citizen scientists, citizen science projects, and citizen science experts.</p> <p>Participatory approaches were designed in this project to take account of and incorporate the views of citizen scientists and citizen science experts in the future development of the GDDS. Our research aimed to (a) extract first-hand knowledge on real world data management practices, (b) obtain views on FAIR and the GDDS initiative, and (c) employ co-design activities to collaboratively identify key obstacles in citizen science data journey and collectively generate ideas on potential ways to address them.</p> <p>This report presents the findings from a series of human-subject studies and co-design workshops with citizen scientists, citizen science projects, and citizen science experts.</p>
Keywords	Citizen Science, FAIR principles, Data Space, Human-Subject Studies, Co-design.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics
CREAF	Centre de Recerca Ecològica i Aplicacions Forestals
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
EC	European Commission
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FIT	Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Information Technology
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GD	Green Deal
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information System
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KWB	Kompetenzzentrum Wasser Berlin
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
ODK	Open Data Kit
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

As proposed by the European Commission (EC), the common European Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) will interconnect currently fragmented and dispersed data from various sources, including citizen science data, to support the objectives of the European Green Deal (GD). To be fit for integration into the GDDS, citizen science data needs to adhere to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) guiding principles that emphasise machine-actionability. While FAIR principles are now widely promoted within citizen science community, implementation of these principles by citizen science initiatives is still limited. Several studies (e.g., Schade and Tsinarakis, 2016; O'Grady and Mangina, 2024) reveal obstacles that citizen science initiatives face when seeking to share their data for re-use outside their projects. Nonetheless, challenges persist, and the available solutions are adopted at a slow pace.

This document is the Deliverable 2.4 for the AD4GD project. It presents the results achieved in the context of Task 2.3 “Defined co-design methodologies for CitSci for Green Deal topics and facilitated convergence to a common semantics” as part of Work Package 2 “In-situ networks, CitSci and Socioeconomic Data”. The document is a follow-up version of the Deliverable 2.3 “CitSci Data Interoperability Obstacles and Solutions” that presented the outcomes of Task 2.2 “Identification of CitSci data including complementary socioeconomic and INSPIRE data”.

Task 2.2 aimed to investigate the state of play with citizen science data in regard to FAIR compliance by examining citizen science project hosting platforms, data hosting platforms, applicable standards, and prominent citizen science initiatives. Building on the results, Task 2.3 focused on engaging with citizen scientists, citizen science projects, and citizen science experts to (a) extract first-hand knowledge on real world data management practices, (b) obtain views on FAIR and the GDDS initiative, and (c) employ co-design activities to collaboratively identify key obstacles in citizen science data journey and collectively generate ideas on potential ways to address them.

Questionnaire-based study

A questionnaire study was carried out with citizen science community to investigate data management practices and to elicit views on FAIR and the GDDS. The survey was completed by 46 respondents; a lower than expected response rate was likely due to community “survey fatigue”. Respondents from diverse types of organisations took part, with a smaller number from governmental organisations and local authorities. Majority of projects were in environmental science (e.g., biodiversity, air quality, water quality, light pollution) and located in Europe. Vast majority of the projects were active and ongoing, operating at a country and regional levels.

The survey revealed that citizen science projects primarily use own infrastructures to host their projects, custom-built tools to collect data, and remote servers hosted by project members to preserve project data. These data management practices can potentially be attributed to institutional constraints, data privacy and ownership concerns, or lack of flexibility of the existing platforms. Projects collect a large variety of data types, making it ever more challenging to find a single suitable repository to preserve or publish all collected data in one place. However, over-reliance on the resources of an organisation or an individual to preserve data can lead to data loss. Most projects collect data with a broad spectrum of purposes in mind, from own organisation’s research to policy influencing, to community building and public education/training. This indicates a good potential for data re-use outside of the project that collected the data.

The survey further revealed that only half of the projects have explicit data management plans, though the majority apply quality control to their data, and nearly half publish their quality control procedures. Just over half of the projects follow formal approaches to structure their data, and only a quarter apply international or community-approved standards. Only half of the projects provide metadata for the data they collect, and less than a quarter follow any formal structured metadata standards. Just a third of the projects use lists of standard terms and around 10% use terms that are documented externally to the project (e.g., formal vocabularies) to describe their data.

Regarding data sharing, vast majority (close to 90%) of the projects make data available for re-use either directly after data acquisition/production or in a staged approach. However, just over half of the projects know the re-use conditions for the data they collect and only a third provide data access and use conditions statements together with their data. Projects use a range of platforms to publish their data, including custom built project websites, national portals, Wikimedia, GBIF, etc., which can significantly affect data discoverability for re-use and complicate data integration.

According to study results, the majority of the projects would be willing to make changes to produce FAIR data and nearly two thirds would be willing to share their data via the GDDS. Nonetheless, many might not have sufficient budget and other resources to achieve this. Lack of resources such as time, money, technical competency, adequate quality assurance and

quality control tools, robust data collection platforms, and human capacity are perceived as major blockers to complying with FAIR and participating in the GDDS. Additionally, projects have concerns with complying to complex standards, data privacy issues, potential complexity of the proposed GDDS system, anticipated barriers for entry and no support for less recognised citizen science stakeholders and projects.

Expert interviews

In preparation for the co-design activities, two interviews with a citizen science expert were conducted to gain a deeper understanding of the issues involved in data management and interoperability. The insights gathered from the citizen science expert highlight the importance of fostering a dialogue around FAIR and CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics) principles. This dialogue should involve various stakeholders, including public authorities, researchers, and the citizens themselves, to ensure that all voices are heard. The dialogue is crucial to facilitate FAIR without overwhelming citizen scientists and ensure data collected by citizens is valuable for policy- and decision-making.

The CARE principles stress the importance of treating communities ethically, including recognising Indigenous Peoples' rights over their data and advancing Indigenous innovation and self-determination. Openness, e.g., transparency about how data is used, and active citizen involvement in citizen science projects, builds trust within the community. Furthermore, addressing technical and legal challenges, such as GDPR compliance and licensing, is essential for data sharing and integration.

The motivations for citizen scientists include personal engagement with local (often environmental) issues, and they seek recognition for their contributions. While citizen science is increasingly recognised in research and policy, it is essential to carefully consider when and how to involve citizens, ensuring their time is used effectively in projects. Long-term citizen engagement can be influenced by personal development opportunities and clear communication strategies.

Scaling citizen science initiatives requires careful consideration and appropriate tools to simplify adherence to FAIR, this is particularly important for smaller or grassroots projects that often have limited resources and will see compliance to any standards as an additional burden.

Co-design workshops

Three co-design workshops were organised with citizen science stakeholders (researchers, local government, citizen science projects) in three domains aligning with the pilot case studies of the AD4GD project: biodiversity, air quality, and water monitoring. Insights from these workshops highlighted specific challenges in each domain.

According to workshop participants, biodiversity domain faces challenges with sustaining citizen engagement and volunteer motivation. Technical challenges included data validation, metadata management, and interoperability. While Darwin Core and GBIF metadata standards could help resolve some of these issues, it appears that some projects have specific requirements that necessitate customised data frameworks and others are not familiar with the existing standards and platforms. It was also reported that projects face weak validation processes, raising concerns over data reliability and consistency. A proposed solution by workshop participants was to facilitate implementation of AI validation and cross-validation among users to enhance data accuracy, similar to successful practices in established platforms like iNaturalist. Additionally, while global repositories like GBIF already collect biodiversity data, smaller projects could benefit from adopting a similar approach to consolidate and share their data more effectively.

Workshops revealed that air quality face major issues with data standardisation, documentation, and privacy. Air quality community is struggling with infrastructure, data storage, data harmonisation from different sources, and legal framework. Commercial cloud dependencies and high costs of sustaining data storage add to technical burdens. Air quality citizen science projects experience gaps in validation and require automated validation and harmonisation with official reference air quality stations. These gaps may be attributed to challenges related to the calibration processes and the accessibility of official data, which hinder effective integration and validation. Workshop participants proposed to develop open-source infrastructures, harmonised APIs for data sharing, and use standardised data formats (e.g., XML, JSON). It should be noted that standardised formats alone will not resolve interoperability issues, harmonised vocabularies and data structures that facilitate seamless integration across diverse datasets are necessary.

Water monitoring citizen science community struggles with short project lifespans and funding limitations, making data quality and sustainability their primary concerns. Data validation is a big challenge, and the projects often overly rely on a single validator, making it hard to ensure consistency and reliability of environmental measurements over time. Due to

funding constraints, it is hard to maintain data archives and preserve historic data for re-use. To tackle these challenges, workshop participants suggested improving training, guidelines, and automated validation tools.

1 INTRODUCTION

When implementing a data space for the European Green Deal (GD), citizen scientists should be considered as valuable data source since their data can potentially fill in the gaps in and complement official data sources. The European Commission (2017) recognises the increasing importance of including citizen-generated data into political decision-making processes. Most recent recommendations by the European Commission (2024) further underscore the need for strong citizen engagement in accelerating the uptake of innovative solutions and developing new technologies, products, and services to address pressing societal challenges.

However, research on data management in citizen science projects shows that data sharing practices and the application of re-use conditions and licensing are often inconsistent, presenting challenges for data interoperability and re-use. According to Schade & Tsinaraki (2016) only 60% of citizen science projects implement a dedicated data management plan, many still lack clearly defined re-use conditions or standardised licensing models, which hinders the data integration at larger scales.

If data from citizen science initiatives are to be included in the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS), the real-world data management practices and challenges of citizen scientists must be understood and considered (Bowser et al., 2023). To address this, participatory approaches were designed in this project to take account of and incorporate the views of citizen scientists and citizen science experts in the future development of the GDDS. As such, this report presents the findings from human-subject studies and co-design workshops with citizen scientists, citizen science projects, and citizen science experts.

The document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 presents the results of a questionnaire-based study conducted by Aston University to **(a)** learn what tools, platforms and standards are currently used by the citizen science projects to collect, store and share project data, **(b)** understand projects' aims and ambitions and identify the perceived blockers to managing and sharing Citizen Science data, and **(c)** gather citizen science community views on the FAIR guiding principles and the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) initiative.
- Section 3 discusses the results of semi-structured interviews with a citizen science expert conducted as part of the preparation for co-design workshops to obtain a deeper understanding of the issues involved in data collection, management and interoperability.
- Section 4 presents the results of three citizen science workshops with key aims to (a) explore challenges in data management and interoperability within citizen science projects, (b) collaboratively identify key obstacles in their data journey, and (c) collectively generate ideas on potential ways to address them.
- Finally, Section 5 offers conclusions.

2 QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY

This section presents the results of a questionnaire-based study conducted by Aston University to investigate current practices used by citizen science projects to collect, structure, document, store, and share their project data. The main focus was on understanding the relevance of FAIR guiding principles for increasing visibility and reuse of citizen science data and citizen science community's perspectives on the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) initiative.

The study was reviewed and approved by the Aston University Ethics Committee and conducted between December 2023 and February 2024 (see Annex I for full study documents). The survey consisted of 43 questions split into following five sections: general information about the project; use of tools in the project lifecycle; data collection and data management practices; project aspirations and wider outreach; and views on the GDDS initiative. A Google Forms-based questionnaire was used to collect survey responses. It was estimated that the questionnaire was to take no more than 25 minutes to complete.

Email invitations to participate were sent to citizen science working groups mailing lists, attendees of and presenters at the 2023 Citizen Science Association (now Association on Advancing the Participatory Sciences (AAPS)) conference and 2022 European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) conference, project managers registered on the EU-Citizen.Science, SciStarter, Anecdata, Zooniverse, Fieldscope, and Globe platforms.

2.1 QUESTIONNAIRE SURVEY RESULTS

A total of 46 valid questionnaire responses were collected. The results are outlined below.

In **Question 1**, survey respondents were asked to describe their organisation (multiple choice), the majority of replies fell under **citizen science projects (46%)**, followed by **for-profit organisations (39%)**, **not-for-profit organisations (37%)**, **research institutes (33%)**, and **education sector (26%)**, see Figure 1.

A single response under the *Other* option was “*startup/independent research organisation*”.

Figure 1: Responses to Question 1 – “Which one(s) of the following best describe your organisation?”.

In **Question 2**, respondents were asked to provide names and URLs of their projects. This data is omitted from the deliverable to keep respondents' identity anonymous. This data was used with respondents' permission to invite them for follow-up interview study.

Question 3 addressed the project topic areas (multiple choice), the most common topic was **environmental science (72%)**, followed by **social science (24%)**, and **the science of citizen science (22%)**, see Figure 2.

Seven responses (27%) under the *Other* option included:

- ethical assessment of AI use in public sector;
- plastic pollution, litter, packaging pollution, extended producer responsibility, open science, open source, open data, geography;
- arthropod monitoring;
- climate change;
- cultural heritage;
- law and engineering; and
- biodiversity.

Figure 2: Responses to Question 3 – “Which topic areas does the project you specified above cover?”.

In **Question 4**, respondents were asked to identify the geographical area(s) where their project is located (multiple choice), the majority of projects were located in **Europe (72%)** followed by **Africa (22%)** and **North America (20%)**, see Figure 3.

Figure 3: Responses to Question 4 – “Where is the project located?”.

In **Question 5**, respondents were asked whether their project was based in a specific country or countries, and if so, to provide the names of these countries. 43 respondents answered this question of which 4 listed more than one country, 2 stated the projects were Europe-wide, 1 listed Central Asia, and 2 stated that the projects were based online. The list of countries specified is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Responses to Question 5 – “If your project is based in a specific country or countries, please specify these?”.

Country	Number of Respondents	Country	Number of Respondents
The Netherlands	6	Central Asia	1
USA	4	Colombia	1
Italy	3	Estonia	1
Portugal	3	Germany	1
Republic of Ireland and Northern Ireland	3	Greece	1
South Africa	3	Haiti	1
Spain	3	Hungary	1
Austria	2	Kenya	1
Belgium	2	Limpopo	1
Europe	2	Tajikistan	1
Sweden	2	Uganda	1
Armenia	1		

In **Question 6**, respondents were asked to specify the geographic coverage of their project (single choice). The majority of projects operated at a **country level (39%)** followed by **reginal (26%)** and **global (15%)**, see Figure 4.

Figure 4: Responses to Question 6 – “Which geographic extent does the project cover?”.

Question 7 addressed the project status; majority of projects were identified as **active (76%)** followed by **completed (11%)**, see Figure 5.

Two responses under the *Other* option included lack of opportunity to continue the project and ongoing activities not specific to one project.

Figure 5: Responses to Question 7 – “What is the current status of this project?”.

In **Question 8**, respondents were asked to state planned duration of their projects (single choice) with the majority of projects specified as **ongoing (no planned end date)** (63%) followed by **1 – 3 years** (22%), see Figure 6. One respondent was not sure about the planned duration.

Figure 6: Responses to Question 8 – “What is the planned duration of the project?”.

Question 9 asked to identify platform(s) used to host citizen science projects (multiple choice), the majority of respondents selected **custom website/webpage** (65%) followed by **Other** (35%), **social media** (28%), and **iNaturalist** (20%), see Figure 7.

Responses provided under the *Other* option are listed in Table 2, it should be noted that 4 respondents listed more than one platform.

Figure 7: Responses to Question 9 – “What data storage facilities do you use to preserve the data collected by your project?”.

Table 2: Responses to Other option of Question 9 – “What data storage facilities do you use to preserve the data collected by your project?”.

Platform	Number of Respondents
EDDMaps (www.eddmaps.org)	1
GitHub	1
Wikimedia	1
EU-Citizen.Science	2
PyBossa	1
Custom built MySQL database for hosting the data	1
iNaturalist	1
Complete information system based on open source and web standards. Backend, webservices and frontend, developed in-house	1
Coreo (https://coreo.io/)	1
Custom website hosted by a botanical organisation	1
Ornitho Euskadi (www.ornitho.eus)	1
Natusfera (https://spain.inaturalist.org/)	1
SACRE (https://seo.org/sacre/)	1
Wordpress	1
QGIS	1
Österreich forscht (www.citizen-science.at)	1
Dark Sky Meter (https://www.darksnymeter.com/)	1
Instagram	1
Facebook	1
X	1
Linkedin	1
Spotteron	1

Question 10 asked to identify tools used for data collection (multiple choice), the majority of respondents selected **custom built web page (40%)** followed by **paper-based datasheets (35%)**, **sensors (28%)**, **basic web-based datasheets (28%)**, and **custom built mobile applications (28%)**, see Figure 8. Data collection tools listed by respondents under the *Other* option are in Table 3.

Figure 8: Responses to Question 10 – “What data collection tools do you use to collect the data from citizen scientists?”.

Table 3: Responses to Question 10’s Other option – “What data collection tools do you use to collect the data from citizen scientists?”.

Data Collection Tools	Number of Respondents
Apps Linked to Dropbox or email (Ruskin, Hydrocolor)	1
EDDMaps, www.eddmaps.org	1
Direct contribution with citation of sources/references	1
A specifically designed manta trawl to collect floating plastics	1
Bat detectors which record ultrasound and GIS data files	1
ApriSensor sensor kits, combined with open data (meteo KNMI, RIVM, CAMS satellite data, etc)	1
Chatbot in Telegram messenger	1
The Dark Sky Meter and Loss of the Night apps	1
Ecosystem Investigation Network	1

Question 11 asked to identify storage facilities used to preserve data collected (single choice), the majority of respondents selected **remote server hosted by a project member (46%)** followed by **remote server hosted by a project member’s institution (28%)**, and the **Other option (26%)**, see Figure 9. Data storage facilities listed by respondents under the *Other* option are in Table 4.

Figure 9: Responses to Question 11 – “What data storage facilities do you use to preserve the data collected by your project?”.

Table 4: Responses to Question 11’s Other option – “What data storage facilities do you use to preserve the data collected by your project?”.

Storage Facility	Number of Respondents
AWS server	2
Mix of local machines of project members and project members institution repository and working toward public repository	1
App platform storage (iNaturalist, EDDMapS)	1
Wikimedia infrastructure	1
All of the first four have been used	1
Hard drives and online databases	1
Commercial server (iAsset)	1
Servers under own management, hardware from service provider	1
Host on our own servers	1
iNaturalist server, then the server of my institution	1
Remote server paid	1

Ten respondents answered **Question 12** regarding the research libraries or public data repositories they use or plan to use to preserve project data. Of these, seven were valid and one was a general comment, valid responses are listed in Table 5.

Table 5: Responses to Question 12 – “If you use research libraries or public data repositories to preserve your project data, please list these below?”.

Research Libraries or Public Data Repositories	Number of Respondents
Working towards using GBIF, Dryad.	1
Herbariums	1
GBIF	2
Zenodo	1
Institution repository	1
4TU.ResearchData	1
ScienceBase	1
Github	1

In **Question 13**, respondents were asked to identify what type(s) of data their projects collect (multiple choice), the majority of respondents selected **observation (76%)** followed by **geolocation (70%)**, **identification (67%)**, **photography (54%)**, **measurement (48%)**, and **classification or tagging (46%)**, see Figure 10. Types of data listed by respondents under the *Other* option are in Table 6 (one response was a general comment).

Figure 10: Responses to Question 13 – “What type(s) of data does your project collect?”.

Table 6: Responses to Question 13’s Other option – “What type(s) of data does your project collect?”.

Types of data	Number of Respondents
Verification	1
Participant	1
Content creation, translation and it structures data which are not currently structured	1
Transcription of interview data and survey data for the social-scientific research that accompanied the CS project	1
Additional data fields apply to some of our surveys, e.g. survey effort	1
Qualitative Data (Microstories collected from Citizens)	1

Question 14 asked for what purpose project data is collected (multiple choice), the majority of respondents selected **education/training (65%)** followed by **own organisation's research (63%)**, **community building (63%)**, and **environmental movement/action (61%)**, see Figure 11. Additional purposes listed by respondents under the *Other* option are in Table 7. Where respondents listed several purposes, these were broken down into separate items.

Figure 11: Responses to Question 14 – “For what purpose(s) does your project collect the data?”.

Table 7: Responses to Question 14's Other option – “For what purpose(s) does your project collect the data?”.

Data Collection Purposes	Number of Respondents
Risk reduction	1
Open Access data for any purpose	3
To provide data to other researches	1
Biodiversity data (Herbarium)	1
Early detection rapid response of invasive species	1
Partners research	1
Marketing of science festivals	1
Science communication training	1
Public engagement and advocacy work	1
Multi-national research	1
Social-scientific data for documentation and community building	1
Awareness-raising about light pollution	1

Question 15 asked whether respondents' organisations had explicit management plans, **52% stated Yes**, see Figure 12.

Figure 12: Responses to Question 15 – “Does your organisation have an explicit data management plan for citizen science projects...?”.

In **Question 16**, projects that had an explicit management plan adopted from external resources were asked to specify these resources. Twelve respondents provided answers to this question of which seven responses were valid, see Table 8. Two respondents were unsure of what data management plan meant.

Table 8: Responses to Question 16 – “If your data management plan is adopted from an external resource, what resource was used?”.

Research Libraries or Public Data Repositories	Number of Respondents
Outline created/tailored based on existing DMP templates (UCSD, NASA, SNF)	1
Own project repository (answer anonymised)	1
AirGIS	1
Based on standards set by the US EPA.	1
Nationale Databank Flora en Fauna (NDFF)	1
Guidelines of own university	1
https://irma.nps.gov/DataStore/Reference/Profile/2291783 ; https://irma.nps.gov/DataStore/Reference/Profile/2293059	1

Question 17 asked whether the project data is quality controlled, the majority of respondents stated **Yes (83%)**, see Figure 13.

Figure 13: Responses to Question 17 – “Is the data collected by the project quality-controlled?”.

In **Question 18**, those projects that apply quality-control to their data were asked whether these quality controls were published, **53% stated Yes** (43% of all respondents), see Figure 14.

Figure 14: Responses to Question 18 – “If ‘yes’, do you publish your quality control protocols?”.

Responses to **Question 19** where respondents were asked to provide links to their quality control specifications are not included in the report to ensure respondents’ anonymity.

Question 20 asked whether respondents follow any formal approach to structure the data they collect, **61% stated Yes**, see Figure 15.

Figure 15: Responses to Question 20 – “Do you follow any formal approach to structure the data you collect?”.

In **Question 21**, those respondents who use formal approaches to structure their data were asked whether they apply international or community-approved standards, **56% stated Yes** (30% of all respondents), see Figure 16. It should be noted that of 28 respondents who use formal approaches, only 25 completed this question.

Figure 16: Responses to Question 21 – “If ‘yes’, do you use international or community-approved standards to structure the data (e.g., WaterML, Darwin Core)?”.

Question 22 asked to list the data standards used, 17 respondents answered of which 3 stated that they were unsure what data standards are being used (see Table 9). Where respondents listed multiple standards, these were broken down into separate items.

Table 9: Responses to Question 22 – “If yes, please list the data standards that are being used:”.

Research Libraries or Public Data Repositories	Number of Respondents
Seismic data standards	1
Darwin Core	9
SOOS	1
US EPA	1
State Dept of Enviro Protection standards	1
Community	1
Project-related approach co-developed by the citizen scientists	1
Data standards from the NDFP	1

Question 23 asked whether respondents provide any metadata for the data they collect, 57% stated Yes, see Figure 17.

Figure 17: Responses to Question 23 – “Do you provide any information that describes and explains the data collected by your project (sometimes this is known as metadata)?”.

In Question 24, those respondents who provide metadata for the data they collect were asked whether they follow any formal structured metadata standards, 65% stated No (33% of all respondents), see Figure 18. It should be noted that of 26 respondents who use formal metadata standards, only 23 completed this question.

Figure 18: Responses to Question 24 – “If ‘yes’, do you follow any formal structured metadata standards...?”.

Question 25 asked to list the metadata standards used, 10 respondents answered of which 1 provided a general comment and 2 stated that they were unsure what metadata standards were being used (see Table 10). Where respondents listed multiple standards, these were broken down into separate items.

Table 10: Responses to Question 25 – “If yes, please list the metadata standards that are being used:”.

Metadata Standards	Number of Respondents
Darwin Core	1
SOOS	1
ERRDAP	1
GBIF Metadata Profile (GMP)	1
US EPA	1
State Dept of Enviro Protection Standard	1
Same as iNaturalist	1
EML	1
4TU.ResearchData metadata	1
GDC CSDGM (Federal Geographic Data Committee Content Standard for Digital Geospatial Metadata)	1

Question 26 asked whether respondents’ projects used lists of standard terms, **72% stated No**, see Figure 19.

Figure 19: Responses to Question 26 – “Are there lists of standard terms that are used in your project?”.

In **Question 27**, those respondents that use lists of standard terms in their projects were asked whether these terms are documented anywhere, **50% stated Yes** (11% of all respondents), see Figure 20. It should be noted that of 13 respondents who use lists of standard terms, only 10 completed this question.

Figure 20: Responses to Question 27 – “If ‘yes’, are these terms documented anywhere, e.g., domain-specific lists of terms, international or community-approved vocabularies...?”.

Question 28 asked to specify where the lists of terms used in the project can be found, 9 respondents answered of which 3 stated that they were unsure (see Table 11).

Table 11: Responses to Question 28 – “If yes, please specify where we can find these lists of terms used in your project:”.

Lists of Terms	Number of Respondents
Currently under development	1
https://dwc.tdwg.org/terms/	1
Water Quality Monitoring	1
Project’s Wiki page	1
https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Help:About_data	1
Taxonomic system of species names	1

Question 29 asked whether respondents make data collected by the project available for reuse, 52% stated Yes (directly after data acquisition/production), 37% stated Yes (in a staged approach, i.e., after an embargo period or quality checking), and 11% stated No, see Figure 21.

Figure 21: Responses to Question 29 – “Do you make the data collected by your project available for re-use?”.

In Question 30, respondents were then asked to explain why they make a particular data sharing decision, 38 respondents provided answers to this open-ended question. Of 5 respondents who stated that they do not make data available for reuse (Question 29), only one provided an explanation stating that their project is “limited on knowledge and specialists”.

Of 24 respondents who answered Yes (directly after data acquisition/production), 23 provided comments. 9 respondents stated that their projects are committed to Open Science principles and believe that “citizen science data should be open and available to everyone”. 8 respondents stated that their projects make data available for reuse by local citizens and people that are not directly involved in the project, other researchers and scientists, land managers, policy makers for achieving improved water quality, and to other stakeholders to e.g. “foster biodiversity knowledge and conservation”. 2 respondents stated that

their projects make data available directly after acquisition because this is the nature of citizen science projects and the projects' social responsibility. 4 respondents stated that sharing data directly after acquisition is part of the projects' own policy or the policy of the application used to collect the data (e.g., iNaturalist).

Of 17 respondents who answered *Yes (in a staged approach...)*, 14 offered further comments. 6 respondents stated that the project data needs to be anonymised, analysed and/or validated before making it available for reuse. 3 stated that the data undergoes quality assurance before being made available. 1 respondent explained that the project data is only available on request which "was decided upon after discussions with the citizen scientists in the project". The remaining 4 responses did not offer direct insights on why the data is released in stages, the respondents explained that: the "project is funded by public money"; their project tries to "fulfil the FAIR principles where possible"; the domain of the project is plastic pollution; and the research partner was responsible for data sharing.

Question 31 asked whether respondents knew the re-use conditions for the data they collect, **61% stated Yes**, also see Figure 22.

Figure 22: Responses to Question 31 – “Do you know the re-use conditions for the data you collect, including any licenses that apply (e.g., Creative Commons licences, Restricted Re-use)?”.

In **Question 32**, for those projects that publish their data and know the re-use conditions, respondents were asked whether they *provide data access and use conditions statements* together with their data, **56% stated Yes (33% of all respondents)**, **34% (20% of all respondents) stated No**, and **11% (1% of all respondents) stated Not Applicable**, also see Figure 23. It should be noted that of 28 respondents who provide data access and use conditions statements (Question 31), only 27 completed this question.

Figure 23: Responses to Question 32 – “If you publish your data and know the re-use conditions, do you provide ‘data access and use conditions’ statements together with your data?”.

Question 33 asked what data publishing facilities are used to share the project data outside of the project (single choice), the majority of respondents selected the *Other option (28%)* followed by *custom built project website (26%)*, and *GBIF (20%)*, see Figure 24. It should be noted that of 46 respondents 41 completed this question.

Additional platforms listed by respondents under the *Other* option are in Table 12.

Figure 24: Responses to Question 33 – “If you publish your data for re-use, what data publishing facilities do you use to share the project data outside of your project?”.

Table 12: Responses to Question 33’s Other option – “If you publish your data for re-use, what data publishing facilities do you use to share the project data outside of your project?”.

Data Publishing Facilities	Number of Respondents
A mix of custom built project website, iNaturalist, GBIF, Dryad	1
Both iNaturalist and GBIF	1
Data can be downloaded from our own system but is also shared to GBIF and EurOBIS	1
4TU.ResearchData	1
EDDMapS	1
U.S. Geological Survey ScienceBase	1
Italian National Biodiversity Network	1
National data portal https://www.waterqualitydata.us/	1
Repository of research institution	1
Web applications and webservice	1
Wikimedia infrastructures	1
Email	1
Own project website	3

Project Aspirations and Wider Outreach

In the next questionnaire section, respondents were asked about their projects’ aspirations and views on FAIR guiding principles.

Project Goals and Aspirations

Questions 34 asked respondents to describe the main goals and aspirations of their citizen science projects. Thematic analysis was applied with **16 themes identified** with educate public, collect data, build knowledge, environment, and biodiversity being most prominent themes.

Educate public: An ambition to educate public through citizen science activities and research findings was one of the most common themes and was reported by 17 respondents. Respondents stated that their projects aim to educate in the areas of air quality, water quality, light pollution, biodiversity, invasive species, climate change, seismic risk, healthcare, polar science, astronomy, maritime cultural heritage, and mercury contamination.

Collect data: 17 respondents reported data collection as one of the aims of their projects. Respondents stated that citizen science can “improve data collection”, “generate comprehensive and credible data on freshwater quality”, “create a network

of low-cost sensors to measure the quality of air and publish indicators online”. Through citizen science “researchers get more data than they could otherwise easily collect”.

Build knowledge: Another prominent theme was an ambition to build knowledge and was reported by 11 respondents. Responses included ambitions to “collectively build knowledge”, “improve knowledge about invasive alien species”, “bring volunteers together with researchers to gain new insights”, “gain valuable insights into [meteor showers] long-term dynamics and behaviours”, “understand sources and transport processes of microplastics floating in the ocean”.

Involve citizens: 9 respondents stated that one of the aims of their projects was to involve citizens in active participation in real research, monitoring activities, and awareness-raising campaigns, and promote “collaboration between citizens, scientific community and institutions”.

Raise awareness: 6 respondents expressed an ambition to raise awareness about light pollution, biological invasions and “the importance of detection, monitoring, control and eradication of invasive alien species”, environmental activities and conservation tasks, and mercury pollution issues.

Connect stakeholders: 6 respondents stated that one of their goals was to connect different stakeholders, to enable citizen science projects to find appropriate partners (by providing a project hosting portal), “create an active collaboration between citizens, scientific community and institutions”, facilitate “cooperation with the regional authorities”, and promote citizen contact with the Green Belt.

Open Data: 5 respondents noted that one of their aims was to make data available to the public, offer records as open access and with open licenses, and to “provide open data, knowledge, tools and support for everyone”.

Research: 7 respondents stated that one of their ambitions was to facilitate or conduct research in the areas of evolution of meteor showers, coastal and plant biodiversity, biological invasions, environmental mercury contamination, safer water bodies for fishing, and artificial lighting. Of these, 2 highlighted their interest in long-term research, i.e., longitudinal studies.

Training: 4 respondents noted that one of their aims was to provide training and support for the tools and citizen science programs they offer.

Schools: Citizen science in schools was mentioned by 6 respondents and was seen as a tool to bring laboratory into practice, an opportunity for pupils and teachers to participate in real research, and a source of state-of-the-art research to integrate into the curriculum. 2 respondents stated that they provide platforms for schools and teachers to share and showcase their events, activities, and projects.

Policy: 5 respondents noted that the data they collect was used to either try to influence policy or directly for policy implementation and informed decision-making. Biodiversity projects were the ones that provided data for policy implementation on invasive species, “species protected by the laws”, and “the development of buffer zones and protective measures to safeguard biota and aquatic communities”.

Environment: Another prominent theme was environment with 11 respondents reporting that their projects collect data related to pollution, health, climate change, and conservation. Respondents reported that they aim to “increase the quality and quantity of environmental data”, “promote the development of environmental activities monitoring of the natural environment encouraging citizen collaboration in conservation tasks”, “promote a healthy physical living environment”, “educate the public on the levels of air pollution”, “highlight the issues of climate change and water quality to the public”, “inform, educate, and forecast exposure and health risks associated with environmental mercury contamination”.

Biodiversity: On a par with environmental research, biodiversity theme was reported by 10 respondents. 4 respondents stated that their activities focus on biodiversity safeguarding and conservation tasks, e.g., to “inform the development of buffer zones and protective measures”. Invasive species monitoring was reported by 3 respondents with a focus on “improving knowledge about invasive alien species [and] raising awareness in society about the importance of detection, monitoring, control and eradication”, “invasive species early detector [and] rapid response”, and “raising awareness about biological invasions, make known the different invasive plants”. Other responses included research into “how climate change is impacting the species, habitats, and communities in our region”, activities to “create a robust baseline dataset for intertidal plant and animal species”, and development of “risk forecasting models to identify safer water bodies for fishing”.

Pollution: 8 respondents reported citizen science focus around pollution, including “taking care of the environment in general to avoid pollution”, “educate the world about the dangers of the light pollution”, “generate comprehensive and credible data on freshwater quality, large-scale irrigation, and agrochemical impacts”, “understand sources and transport

processes of microplastics floating in the ocean”, “inform, educate, and forecast exposure and health risks associated with environmental mercury contamination”.

Water quality: 6 respondents stated that their projects were in water quality domain and aimed to “generate comprehensive and credible data on freshwater quality”, “teach people about river health” and “highlight the issues of ... water quality to the public”, and “develop risk forecasting models to identify safer water bodies for fishing”. 1 respondent explained that their organisation “has built several tools to increase the quality and quantity of environmental data collected by community science organizations” for marine and freshwater water quality monitoring.

Air quality: 5 respondents stated that their projects were in air quality domain aiming to “educate the public on the levels of air pollution”, “highlight and monitor air quality levels (NO2) in Italian cities”, “create a network of low-cost sensors to measure the quality of air and publish indicators online”, and empower citizens in air quality monitoring.

Platforms and tools: 8 respondents reported that their projects offered citizen science platforms and tools to enable project sharing, data collection, quality assurance, data storage, and data sharing for re-use.

FAIR Awareness and Willingness / Capacity to Comply

Question 35 asked whether respondents were aware of the FAIR guiding principles before participating in this survey, **61% stated Yes**, see Figure 25. It should be noted that of 46 respondents 45 completed this question. One respondent who omitted this question commented that the project was completed and the data made available.

Figure 25: Responses to Question 35 – “Were you aware of the FAIR guiding principles before participating in this survey?”.

Question 31 asked how likely they would be to make changes to their project management to produce data that aligns with FAIR (single choice), the majority of respondents selected **very likely (56%)** and **likely (28%)** followed by **unsure (28%)**, see Figure 26. It should be noted that of 46 respondents 44 completed this question.

Figure 26: Responses to Question 36 – “How likely are you to make changes to your project management to produce data that aligns with FAIR and can be reused outside of your project? This includes adopting new tools, platforms and guidelines.”.

4 respondents who stated that they are very unlikely or unlikely to make changes (**Question 36**) commented that this decision was because: data is already open; the project is completed and it is not possible to make changes; project already adheres to FAIR; and because the data collection platform is independent from respondent’s organisation.

Of 10 respondents who were unsure of whether they would make changes, 8 offered further comments. One respondent stated that they were “*not familiar with this specific acronym but very familiar with the concepts of data quality, documentation and openness.*”. While this respondent was “*intrigued and bit perplexed by the machine automation component of FAIR, however [they] see great value in this but also risk in data misuse.*”. Two respondents stated that adherence to FAIR would depend on the benefits to the projects and difficulty to implement. Other two respondents stated that complying to FAIR would come down to time, resources, and prioritisation but the “*restructuring that would need to happen would probably be placed below other job duties*”. Two respondents stated that their decision was driven by the platforms they use – a National Biodiversity Data Centre which operates within the GBIF framework and iNaturalist tool. One respondent commented that their organisation was “*in a review process to overhaul and clarify [their] data management practices*”.

Of 30 respondents who stated that they were likely or very likely to make changes (**Question 36**), 25 provided further comments. 5 respondents stated that they strongly believe in supporting Open Science and Open Data policy and “*want [the project] data to be available to everyone*”. 5 respondents commented that they want their project data to be available for reuse to “*promote knowledge transfer*”, “*change legislation and prosecutions*”, and “*make the data as impactful as possible*”. One of these respondents stated that they “*don't want the great data collected by participants to languish on a computer somewhere and the faster land managers can access the data the quicker problems can be addressed*”. 4 respondents stated that they already adhere to FAIR guiding principles, “*but if anything is missing, [they] would be willing to change it*”. 3 respondents stated that adhering to FAIR principles would help “*improve the project standards*”, “*empower [the] project*”, and help to “*be at same level with other projects*”. One respondent commented that FAIR principles are deemed relevant and important since these are being discussed by the citizen science community.

Perceived Advantages and Disadvantages of Complying with FAIR

Question 38 asked to identify perceived advantages of producing data that aligns with FAIR principles, 34 respondents provided comments.

12 respondents agreed that the main advantage would be increased data visibility for reuse and data exploitation capacity by decision makers and other third parties. One of these respondents commented that FAIR principles could ensure that “*people can see and use the data that has been collected through a citizen science effort, especially for one of the most data limited regions of the world*”. 3 respondents stressed the importance of Open Science stating that “*Open Science is the real science*”, “*data gathered by the public should be made available to the public and not stay in a solely academic environment*”, and Open Science “*provides an alternative to a currently dominant closed data access*”. 3 respondents commented that FAIR can increase data and project findability and visibility with one suggesting that this “*broadens potential uses and applications*”. Other 3 respondents stated that FAIR is useful overall without providing further insights.

Other comments on the advantages of FAIR included:

- making data as user-friendly as possible;
- reliability and accuracy of data;
- usefulness, ease of use and credibility of data;
- production of knowledge;
- reproducibility of the published results;
- interoperability;
- access to research for a wide range of interested parties;
- updating of data-sets, acknowledgment and recognition of contributors, supporting research activities;
- more scientific value;
- building of community; and
- making research easy.

Question 39 asked to identify perceived disadvantages of producing data that aligns with FAIR principles, 34 respondents provided comments.

12 respondents agreed that the main obstacle would be lack of resources such as time and money or project capacity. One of these respondents offered an insightful discussion:

“This is a HUGE task, a full-time job for one person, there are so many standards for each type of data, so many repositories to choose from, so many naming schemes to [be] decided upon. To truly make all data types FAIR it will require a great deal

of Metadata standardization and organization of all our data products (from physical sample, to raw data, to processed and finalized data). Any help, tools, resources, coordination efforts is greatly appreciated.”

8 respondents raised concerns over GDPR, policies and licensing, national legislations on privacy issues, data sovereignty and also data privacy concerning indigenous communities. One of these respondents also commented that it is “difficult to understand the opinions of the people providing the data. As it is their data, it is important to understand how they would like it to be handled.”.

2 respondents commented that there is “lack of knowledge on tools that support FAIR principles” and there should be “good examples that institutes can “copy”, and good examples of what not to do”. Another respondent elaborated that “we explain FAIR principles in a very complex way. I think tools need to guide people in adding metadata, uploading data with correct formats and open licenses/tools, adding identifiers and so on. this is simple and it is how it should be managed. Not by explaining the concept of metadata.”.

Others stated that “FAIR principles are often difficult to comply with”, their organisation has “different agendas and research competitiveness”, and there are issues with reliability and standardisation.

One respondent expressed concerns over machine- findability, accessibility, interoperability and reuse, commenting that “relying on computers to appropriately discern and filter through datasets is a bit concerning as there is a high degree of human decision making that takes place when evaluating data for specific environmental uses”.

Views on the Green Deal Data Space

Question 40 asked whether respondents were aware of the Green Deal Data Space initiative before completing the questionnaire, the majority stated **No (87% of all survey respondents)**, see Figure 27. It should be noted that of 46 respondents 44 answered this question.

Figure 27: Responses to Question 40 – “Were you aware of the Green Deal Data Space initiative before participating in this survey?”.

Question 41 asked whether respondents would be willing to share their citizen science data via the Green Deal Data Space, the majority of respondents answered **Yes (directly after data acquisition/production) (40% of all survey respondents)**, followed by **I do not know (28% all survey respondents)** and **Yes (in a staged approach, ...) (24% all survey respondents)** (see Figure 28). It should be noted that of 46 respondents 44 answered this question.

2 respondents who selected *Other*, stated that they would make data available “after making sure [they] first checked off other commitments for sharing the data” and “at raw format [or in] processed format if there is funding to pay for the processing costs”. One respondent who selected *Other* commented that their project data is already shared via GBIF and it would be redundant to share it directly via another platform.

Figure 28: Responses to Question 41 – “Would you be willing to share your citizen science project data via the Green Deal Data Space (or a similar initiative, if your project is not located in Europe)?”.

Question 42 asked to identify perceived advantages of participating in the Green Deal Data Space or a similar initiative, 30 answered this question.

11 respondents identified **data sharing** as one of the potential advantages. Respondents commented that “*data sharing would be easier*”, “*the more we can all share data the better [since] it’s hard to know what will one day be useful and meaningful*”. Others suggested that the GDDS would allow “*reaching out more users of data*” and “*the use of the data [would be] maximized*” with “*increased data exploitation capacity*”. One respondent highlighted data visibility stating that the GDDS could help “*make research data more visible and available beyond the often very local approach of CS projects*”.

6 respondents stated that the GDDS could enable **collaboration**, including “*participating in non-USA centric efforts*”, “*collaborating with leading scientists*”, “*interconnection with other tools/data /projects*”. One respondent further commented that “*seeing each other’s data can inspire and produce collaborations*”.

4 respondents noted potential benefits of **outreach** for their projects, datasets, and the environmental issues being researched.

Other potential benefits identified included support and funding, making data comparable, data licensing, open access, and “*the scale of GDDS and the trustworthiness of a European commission*”.

Question 42 asked to identify perceived major barriers to participating in the Green Deal Data Space or a similar initiative, 29 answered this question.

13 respondents commented that the main barriers would be **lack of resources to enable participation**, of these 6 respondents identified lack of funding as the primary obstacle. Others highlighted lack of human resources, time, knowledge required, quality assurance and quality control tools, “*robust platforms that can collect the right/needed variables*”.

3 respondents stated that better understanding of the GDDS would be required before participating. Other 2 respondents suggested the need in knowing the standards involved.

Other respondents noted data privacy issues, potential complexity of the proposed system and the need for training programs, anticipated barriers for entry and no support for less recognised citizen science stakeholders and projects – one respondent expressed a great concern that he/she would not receive nearly as much support as the established researchers.

2.2 RESULTS SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

While an ambition for this study was to collect over 100 valid responses, only 46 responses were collected despite 3 rounds of email invitations and considerably large mailing list (over 500 contacts). Such low response rate can potentially be attributed to another similar questionnaire study that was conducted in spring 2023 with the resulting dataset and high-level study analysis published in July 2024 (O’Grady and Mangina). The study by O’Grady and Mangina recruited participants from the same citizen science communities approached by this study. It can be speculated that by the time this study was advertised, willing participants already developed a “survey fatigue”.

Respondents from diverse types of organisations took part in the questionnaire study, including citizen science projects, for-profit organisations, not-for-profit organisations, research institutes, and education sector, although many respondents identified themselves with more than one type. There were a smaller number of respondents from governmental organisations and local authorities, which is somewhat not surprising since, at present, citizen science activities are primarily run by non-governmental organisations. Governmental organisations largely act as citizen science data consumers or work in collaboration with citizen science projects to improve their decision making and legislations.

Project topics mainly fell under environmental science (e.g., biodiversity, air quality, water quality, light pollution). Most projects were located in Europe which was perhaps influenced by the study dissemination mailing list which was based on public contacts from conferences and platforms located in Europe and the US. There was an even spread of countries where the projects were conducted, with the Netherlands being most prominent and mentioned by 6 respondents. The majority of projects operated at a country and regional levels, indicating projects' focus on local issues.

Vast majority of projects were active and ongoing (with no planned end date), possibly involving longitudinal studies with either data gathering campaigns or continuously collected data. As was discussed in the deliverable D2.2, data storage for re-use is a real challenge for majority of citizen science projects, especially those collecting continuous data streams.

Majority of projects use own infrastructure (custom website/webpage) to host their projects. The reason behind this might be institutional constraints (legal aspects of using 3rd party platforms), data privacy and ownership concerns, or insufficient flexibility of the existing platforms to fulfil project requirements.

Majority of projects use custom-built data collection tools (paper-based, web-based, mobile apps) opposed to using off-the-shelf toolkits like ODK ¹ or CitSci². Technical competency required to set up and run open-source software, insufficient customisation of free tools, lack of monetary resources to pay for commercial services might be some of the reasons behind choosing custom-built solutions. Based on anecdotal knowledge, some smaller-scale projects rely on technical competence of volunteers to develop data collection apps or set up web forms.

For some projects, data privacy, data ownership and legal concerns might prevent them from using off-the-shelf solutions. While it was somewhat surprising that many projects rely on paper-based datasheets, perhaps this medium is more intuitive for citizen scientists and, in some cases, is the only viable solution, e.g., in the regions where mobile devices are less affordable. For the projects however data digitalisation from paper requires substantial resources and can be prone to human error. It was also revealed that many projects use sensors to collect their data, although no information was gathered on the types of sensors used.

Regarding data preservation, the study revealed that the majority of projects use remote servers hosted by the project members. It is concerning that preservation of citizen science data is often dependent on resources of an organisation or an individual and valuable data might be lost. Repositories such as Zenodo ³ might not be seen as suitable for many projects that do not directly produce scientific outputs. Additionally, project organisations' data policy or legal concerns (e.g., GDPR) might prevent projects from preserving data in public repositories.

Citizen science projects collect a variety of data types, including observation, geolocation, identification, photography, measurement, classification or tagging, specimen/sample, sample analysis, with no data type being particularly dominant. Diversity of the data collected by a single project makes it ever more difficult to find a single suitable repository to publish all collected data in one place. There is no dominant purpose for which data is collected; projects collect data for education/training, own organisation's research, community building, environmental movement/action, policy making, local authority decision support, etc. This is encouraging from a data re-use perspective since data is not collected solely for own research needs.

The study revealed that only half of the projects have explicit data management plans, though the majority apply quality control to their data, and nearly half publish their quality control procedures. Just over half of the projects follow formal approaches to structure their data; only a quarter apply international or community-approved standards with Darwin Core being most applied standard. Respondents were not specifically asked whether their projects are in biodiversity, hence it is impossible to say how many of the biodiversity projects apply Darwin Core.

¹ <https://getodk.org/>

² <https://citsci.org/>

³ <https://zenodo.org/>

Only half of the projects provide metadata for the data they collect, less than a quarter follow any formal structured metadata standards. Just a third of the projects use lists of standard terms and around 10% use terms that are documented externally to the project (e.g., formal vocabularies).

Close to 90% of the projects make data available for re-use – half of the projects directly after data acquisition/production, and nearly 40% in a staged approach after an embargo period, quality assurance, anonymisation, data analysis and validation.

Just over half of the projects know the re-use conditions for the data they collect and only third provide data access and use conditions statements together with their data. Given that vast majority of citizen science projects make data available for external use, it is concerning that many do not know or explicitly state data licensing conditions.

Projects use a wide range of platforms to publish their data, including custom built project websites, national portals, Wikimedia, GBIF, etc. This significantly hinders data discoverability for re-use by interested parties since they are unlikely to know about individual project websites or institutional portals. Not all data portals offer standardised APIs, while custom project websites or institutional platforms are unlikely to offer APIs at all affecting data integration.

Regarding aspirations, projects often have more than one goal, where most common ones include:

- educating public about science and global or local issues;
- building knowledge, gaining valuable insights, and raising awareness;
- collecting larger quantities of data as well as collecting comprehensive and credible data;
- conducting environmental research in biodiversity, air quality, water quality, and light pollution;
- involving citizens and connecting them with other stakeholders;
- influencing policy and decision-making of governmental bodies; and
- offering platforms and tools for project dissemination, data collection, quality assurance, data storage, and data sharing for re-use.

Over half of the projects were aware of FAIR guiding principles prior to participating in the study and the majority would be willing to make changes to produce data that aligns with FAIR. Projects see the advantages of FAIR in increased: data visibility for re-use; data interoperability; data exploitation capacity by decision makers and other third parties; data openness; data credibility; data accessibility and ease of use; data reliability and accuracy; reproducibility of scientific results; and scientific value of data. The study however revealed that there is a big misconception of what FAIR actually means with many projects assuming that FAIR implies Open Data.

Only 10% of the projects were aware of the GDDS initiative before the study, but nearly two thirds of the projects would be willing to share their data via the GDDS directly after data acquisition or in a staged approach. Projects see the advantages of the GDDS initiative in increased: data sharing, data visibility; pool of data re-users; data exploitation capacity; collaboration of different stakeholders; project outreach; data compatibility and comparability; and visibility of licensing.

Positive attitudes towards FAIR and the GDDS initiative are extremely encouraging, however many projects might not have sufficient budget and other resources to ensure that their data is FAIR and interoperable with the GDDS. Lack of resources such as time, money, technical competency, adequate quality assurance and quality control tools, robust data collection platforms, and human capacity are perceived by the projects as major blockers to complying with FAIR and participating in the GDDS. Additionally, projects have concerns with complying to various complex standards (including knowing what standards are even relevant), data privacy issues, potential complexity of the proposed GDDS system, anticipated barriers for entry and no support for less recognised citizen science stakeholders and projects.

3 CITIZEN SCIENCE EXPERT INTERVIEWS

In this section, we discuss the results of semi-structured interviews with a citizen science expert conducted by FIT as part of the preparation for co-design workshops presented in Section 5.

In preparation for the co-design activities to involve citizen scientists, a deeper understanding of the issues involved in data collection, management and interoperability needed to be gained. Therefore, the first activity was to conduct an explorative semi-structured interview with a citizen science expert to gain insights into the community. The first interview was supplemented by a follow-up second interview in order to explore further questions and clarify ambiguities.

The take-aways provided basis for the chosen workshop design and covered the following topics: Understanding the Engagement of Citizens in Citizen Science, Motivation for Long-Term Engagement, Avoiding Leaving Communities Alone, Interoperability Challenges, Scaling up Citizen Science, FAIR Data Principles in Citizen Science, Challenges and Solutions for FAIR Data, Vision for Future Citizen Science and Data Management, Integration into Data Governance, Trust and Openness, and Demand for a dialogue.

3.1 INSIGHTS INTO CITIZEN SCIENCE EXPERTISE FROM INTERVIEWS

From the interviews' insights gathered, it could be stated that there should be a dialogue about the FAIR principles in the context of citizen science, particularly to ensure that FAIR principles are understood and appropriately applied without overburdening citizen scientists. Interviews also revealed the importance of discussing inclusiveness and openness (included in the CARE principles) to build trust and ensure that all citizen scientists feel respected and valued. It is important to involve various stakeholders which requires a structured dialogue with different groups, including public authorities, researchers, and the citizens themselves, to ensure that all voices are heard and that the process is inclusive and effective. There is a remaining demand for ongoing dialogue between citizen scientists and policymakers. This dialogue is essential to ensure that the data collected by citizen scientists is useful and recognized in policy-making processes. The need for discussions about how data is used, what data is needed, and how it can influence decision-making was emphasized in the interviews. Further, the interviewed insights highlighted that there is a need for a dialogue with citizen scientists to understand the desired conditions for data access and use. There is a movement to have citizen science data as open as possible, but there is also a responsibility to discuss potential sensitivity and privacy issues.

The interviews revealed valuable insights into citizen scientist engagement that are important to consider when addressing and involving this target group. The following section states insights extracted from the expert interviews and reflects the expert's opinions which are based on their professional and contextualized experience in data and citizen science. The interest in involving citizen scientists lies both on the part of the research and political development of a solution for the Green Deal, but the citizen scientists themselves also want to be heard and involved in political development. Citizen scientists often engage to address environmental issues, such as noise, odor, or air pollution, driven by personal stakes rather than purely scientific interest, and those issues have usually clear effects at local level. Historical perceptions of citizen science as a cost-saving measure for research shifted toward recognizing the value of citizens' contributions, including shaping research questions and ensuring data quality. Citizen science is increasingly seen as a loop involving policy-making, with citizens contributing to decision-making and monitoring political impacts. But it is important to keep in mind that citizen science does not necessarily mean that everybody should always be engaged. When and how to engage volunteers needs to be considered carefully, following a plan of what should be achieved in the time that they dedicate to a citizen science project.

The motivations for long-term engagement in citizen science projects vary and are significantly influenced by the offerings provided to citizens and the recognition of their time. Participants are often driven by a desire to stay connected with their communities, address local issues, and pursue personal development opportunities, such as training programs. It is important to note that continuous engagement is not always necessary; projects should establish clear engagement plans that include communication strategies and post-project community management. Furthermore, projects can emerge from grassroots initiatives, in which case it is the community's responsibility to manage their evolution. Conversely, projects may also be part of larger programs aimed at promoting openness and democracy, allowing for longer-term engagement where the nature of participation may evolve over time.

When projects conclude, having a plan for the community's next steps is crucial. This approach aligns with the CARE principles, which emphasize treating communities with care, respect, and inclusiveness rather than leaving them without guidance or further engagement. A key aspect of the CARE principles is the recognition of Indigenous Peoples' rights regarding their data throughout the data lifecycle. In the context of citizen science, ethical data management and participant well-being are paramount. The CARE principles advocate for inclusiveness, ethical governance, and respect for communities, ensuring they are not left isolated and are supported throughout and after the project. Importantly, communities should have a voice in how their data is utilized.

While the FAIR principles are essential for data management, they do not address the principle of openness in terms of project transparency, which should be emphasized in discussions about citizen science. Openness fosters transparency and builds trust within communities, as participants need to understand how their data will be used and what to expect from the project.

Successful citizen science initiatives also face interoperability challenges, which encompass technical, semantic, organizational, legal, and cultural aspects. Projects should leverage open standards and existing infrastructures to facilitate data integration and sharing (to be reused by researchers, authorities, other citizen science projects), thereby reducing technical barriers. Legal considerations, including GDPR compliance, are critical for ensuring that data collected by citizens is recognized and trusted.

Scaling in citizen science can take various forms, including upscaling (from local to national levels), scaling out (replication in similar contexts), scaling deep (engaging more diverse participants), and scaling back (refining project scope). A notable resource for understanding these dynamics is the Mutual Learning Exercise (European Commission, n.d.), which can be consulted for additional insights.

The FAIR data principles must be balanced with the inclusiveness advocated by the CARE principles and the practicalities of citizen science. Responsibility for ensuring compliance with FAIR principles lies with appropriate project partners, who should engage in dialogue with citizen scientists. There may be tension between the immediate goals of citizen scientists and the long-term demands of FAIR compliance, as citizen scientists often focus on tangible outcomes while FAIR principles introduce complexities related to data management and re-usability.

To address these challenges, it is proposed that rather than placing the full burden of understanding and applying FAIR principles on citizen scientists, support should be provided through existing data management infrastructures. This approach empowers citizen scientists by offering tools and systems that automatically align with FAIR principles, thus reducing their need to navigate these complexities independently. Simplifying the FAIR principles or providing infrastructures that handle the technical aspects could enable citizen scientists to contribute data without extensive concerns about compliance.

Recognizing that small or locally active citizen science groups may not have the capacity to fully understand and implement FAIR principles, it becomes clear that expecting them to do so may be unreasonable. A proportional approach is necessary, where the application of FAIR principles is tailored to the context and scope of each project. Not every citizen science project requires strict adherence to these principles, particularly smaller or less formal initiatives.

In light of these challenges, providing supportive infrastructures can assist small citizen science groups in applying FAIR principles. Ensuring data is findable and accessible often involves simplifying metadata creation and aligning citizen science data with existing research and public sector standards. Furthermore, the principle of openness should be discussed consistently in citizen science contexts, as it plays a vital role in data management.

Looking ahead, the vision for citizen science and data management includes the establishment of more open research infrastructures that support citizen science while respecting diverse methodologies. A broader and inclusive approach to data governance is essential for integrating citizen science into the wider research and policy ecosystem. Continuous dialogue and the involvement of various stakeholders will be crucial for aligning citizen science with national and international data policies.

Additionally, citizen science activities should be viewed within the broader context of data governance and emerging practices, such as the Data Governance Act in the European Union. Trust and openness are critical elements; citizen scientists must feel confident that their data will be used appropriately and that they will be informed about how their contributions impact broader scientific and policy-making efforts.

4 CITIZEN SCIENCE WORKSHOPS

This section presents the results of three citizen science workshops conducted by FIT in collaboration with KWB, CREAM, ECMWF and Aston University project partners. The key aims of the workshops were to (a) explore challenges in data management and interoperability within citizen science projects, (b) collaboratively identify key obstacles in their data journey, and (c) collectively generate ideas on potential ways to address them.

Ensuring interoperability across diverse data sources, platforms, and stakeholders remains a significant challenge in integrating citizen science data into structured frameworks such as the Green Deal Data Space. Despite its potential, citizen science faces challenges in ensuring data interoperability, for example, because citizen science data often originates from heterogeneous sources, which limits its broader uptake and effectiveness in supporting policy decisions (European Commission, 2020). To address these challenges, a workshop series engaging citizen science communities from three different domains was developed and conducted, aiming to identify key interoperability obstacles and explore solutions through co-design. Co-design here refers to the definition previously made for the project AD4GD (AD4DG Project 101061001. Deliverable 1.1 - Multi-actor and knowledge centres co-design and requirements definition report). Co-design is a participatory approach where users (or stakeholders) are not just participants providing feedback, but active collaborators in the design process, ensuring that their experiences, needs, and expertise shape the development of solutions. It extends Human-Centered Design (HCD) by fostering collaborative decision-making and mutual learning, rather than simply gathering user feedback. The approach incorporates various methods, selected based on domain knowledge and resource availability.

To foster discussions on the practical integration of citizen science data, the workshop series was structured to address both regional and international challenges while maintaining applicability to different domains. A more generic workshop concept was initially developed and then iteratively tailored for three distinct use cases: water monitoring, biodiversity, and air quality. These use cases directly correlate to the pilots in the AD4GD project. This approach allowed for a targeted exploration of domain-specific challenges, particularly in data governance and interoperability, while ensuring that methodologies remained structured yet adaptable to varying citizen science contexts.

4.1 WORKSHOP OBJECTIVES

Key Goals: The primary goal of these workshops was to facilitate a structured dialogue to gather and learn from the experiences of citizen science experts in the three use cases — water monitoring, biodiversity, and air quality — across all phases of the data life cycle, from data creation and collection to data deletion. Further, the workshops aimed to identify key challenges in integrating citizen science data into broader environmental monitoring frameworks and structured data spaces, to discuss solutions for improvements and for aligning citizen science data with existing European standards, such as INSPIRE Directive, to ensure standards defined for the Green Deal Data Space are met.

FAIR Principles and Interoperability Challenges: While a majority of citizen science projects provide access to raw or aggregated data, a survey from the European Commission (2016) found that the exact usage conditions are not always well-defined or lack clear licensing. This ambiguity in data usage conditions is particularly relevant as citizen science data must meet FAIR criteria, it can create barriers to effective data sharing across different platforms and studies. An example platform that addresses these challenges is AirSensEUR, it demonstrates how INSPIRE-compliant data management strategies can facilitate harmonized data exchange (Kotsev et al., 2017).

In consideration of these insights, the workshops were designed to bridge the gap between citizen science data practices and formal environmental data infrastructures, such as the Green Deal Data Space. The chosen workshop format can be understood as a method to gather knowledge from experts of the field on the following question: **How might we ensure that citizen-generated data can be effectively leveraged within the Green Deal Data Space?**

4.2 WORKSHOP DESIGN & METHODOLOGY

In this section, we outline the approach used to develop co-design methodologies for citizen science in the context of Green Deal topics. Our process focused on facilitating convergence toward a common semantics, ensuring that diverse stakeholders could collaboratively find the solutions to address data interoperability challenges. Additionally, insights from Citizen Science Expert Interviews (Section 4) were integrated to refine the methodological framework, aligning it with the practical

experiences and needs of the contexts of the pilot use cases. From the interviews with a citizen science expert it can be stated that, according to the expert opinions, citizen scientists should not be in the role of having to fulfil FAIR criteria. Citizen scientists should not have to be made aware of FAIR and bear the additional work involved, as they are already collecting data voluntarily and free of charge. The overall aim of citizen science is to solve social and environmental problems (Guasch, 2022) and should not require one to be a technical expert (e.g. in FAIR) to carry out the data collection. In order to enhance an understanding of the perspectives related to the Green Deal Data Space, informal interviews were conducted with experts in FAIR principles. The first interview served as an initial clarification and overview of key concepts, while a subsequent follow-up interview provided a deeper understanding and addressed questions that arose following discussions with the citizen science expert and the review of the first draft of the workshop concept. These interviews revealed that, from this perspective, only those who are the originators of the data - i.e. only those who collect the data, in the case of citizen science the citizen scientists - could enter metadata, make data available, include recognized semantic vocabularies and defined licences to comply with FAIR. From these insights the following question arose: **Who is responsible for fulfilling FAIR principles?**

Format: The format of workshops was chosen for each AD4GD pilot (Biodiversity, Water Monitoring, Air Quality) based on pilot's needs and stakeholder availability. The workshop for Biodiversity Pilot was conducted on-site in Catalonia. The other two workshops took place remotely via Microsoft Teams. All workshops followed a common agenda, but appropriate adaptations were made to best facilitate each Pilot workshop (e.g., using physical paper, pens, and sticky notes instead of Miro Board for in-person Biodiversity workshop). The adaptations were planned and implemented together with the project partners of each pilot case study.

Target Audience: The workshops were designed to engage key stakeholders previously defined for each pilot during the pilot kick-off (deliverable No: D6.1, pilot technical implementation planning, implementation and assessment), taking into account their relation to the pilot and relevance to the project, as established in the kick-off phase. Furthermore, the quadruple helix model (Schütz et al., 2019) was applied to ensure a diverse and balanced representation of stakeholders from four key sectors: civil society, business, government, and academia.

Figure 29: The Quadruple Helix Model adapted by Fraunhofer (2016), originally developed by Carayannis and Campbell (2009). Copyright © 2015 Fraunhofer (Schütz et al., 2019).

This model facilitates multi-actor collaboration, fostering innovation and ensuring that co-design methodologies reflect the needs and expertise of a broad range of participants. The application of the quadruple helix model is aligned with approaches used in other EU-funded projects, such as the Cos4Cloud project (European Open Science Cloud), which successfully integrated this framework into its co-design methodology to engage different stakeholder groups in the development of

citizen science services (Cos4Cloud, 2024). By adopting a similar approach, these workshops aimed to maximize engagement, ensuring that insights from all four sectors contribute to shaping interoperability and to create a constructive discussion to design initial solutions.

Facilitation Approach: The facilitation approach emphasizes interactive discussions and hands-on exercises to actively engage citizen science communities in identifying interoperability obstacles related to citizen science data. Utilizing co-design methodologies, participants collaboratively shared their challenges and explored ideas for solutions that foster convergence, upscaling, and continuity within Green Deal topics. Through motivational and participatory techniques, the workshops ensured that stakeholders contributed valuable insights and drafts for solutions.

Activities and Tools Used: The workshop employed a structured co-design approach, guiding participants through a transition from data providers (data creation and sharing) to data consumers (data re-use) offering a framework to share their specific interoperability challenges from multiple perspectives. The applied methodologies and activities were based on a data journey mapping including a pain point identification to uncover key obstacles in citizen science data usage within each use case. The results were then analyzed to extract commonalities and differences between the use cases.

The Data Journey is based on the Data Life Cycle (Boukhers, 2023). In addition to the existing Data Life Cycle, a “Maintain” phase has been added to represent relevant steps for a data space, which is then the 8th phase - it is categorised after the “Share & Exchange” phase and is followed by the “Reuse” phase.

Figure 30: Visualisation of the Data Life Cycle used in three co-design workshops (figure created by CREAM).

The data journey used in the workshops was therefore structured as follows:

- **Create & Collect:** Issues during data generation or gathering.
- **Clean:** Obstacles related to data preparation.
- **Validate:** Challenges in ensuring data quality.
- **Document:** Problems in describing or annotating data.
- **Store:** Issues with saving or storing data securely.
- **Use:** Barriers to accessing or analyzing data.
- **Share & Exchange:** Problems with data dissemination or collaboration.
- **Maintain:** Challenges in updating or ensuring the long-term usability of data.
- **Reuse:** Issues in repurposing data for new applications.
- **Archive/Delete:** Problems related to final storage or data destruction.

These methods were designed to help workshop participants systematically analyze obstacles and identify opportunities for improvement.

Data Collections Methods: The workshop employed a combination of recordings, Miro boards, and structured group discussions to capture insights on data interoperability challenges and potential solutions. In remote settings, Miro, a digital collaboration tool, served as an interactive whiteboard, allowing participants to visually contribute and engage in real-time. This approach fosters dynamic discussions and enhances idea exchange by providing a shared digital space for co-creation. For the face-to-face Barcelona workshop, participants were provided with physical materials (such as brown paper and post-its) and were digitised afterwards for the analysis.

4.3 WORKSHOP PARTICIPANTS

Categorisation

- Moderators/Admins: Individuals in these roles are not counted as participants.
- Participants: This group is further divided into two subcategories:
 - Internals: This includes project partners from the AD4GD consortium and related speakers.
 - Externals: Individuals who are neither part of the consortium nor affiliated with its organizations.
- Affiliation Areas: Both internal and external participants are categorized based on their registration forms, which include areas such as 'Civil Society,' 'Academia,' and others.

Water Monitoring Workshop

- Moderators/Admins: 2
- Participants: 8
 - Internal Participants: 3
 - Academic Institution: 1
 - Civil Society: 2
 - External Participants: 5
 - Administration/Authority: 3
 - Academic Institution: 3
 - Civil Society: 1
 - Industry: 0
 - None: 1

Biodiversity Workshop

- Moderators/Admins: 1
- Participants: 12
 - Internal Participants: 4
 - External: 8
 - Administration/Authority: 0
 - Academic Institution: 7
 - Civil Society: 1
 - Industry: 0

Air Quality Workshop

- Moderators/Admins: 3
- Participants: 19
 - Internal Participants: 3
 - Administration/Authority: 1
 - Academic Institution: 2
 - External Participants: 16
 - Administration/Authority: 3
 - Academic Institution: 7
 - Civil Society: 3
 - Industry: 2
 - None: 1

4.4 USE-CASE-SPECIFIC INSIGHTS AND CHALLENGES

Air Quality Workshop: The air quality workshop participants contribute expertise in atmospheric science and pollution monitoring, particularly in tracking pollutants like PM_{2.5} and NO_x within regulatory thresholds. Their strengths are primarily in data standardization and API development, which emphasize harmonized formats (XML, JSON, CSV) and open-source infrastructure. However, it is important to note that the use of low-cost sensors in citizen science initiatives presents challenges in calibration, impacting the accuracy of air quality measurements. Additionally, regulatory compliance and privacy laws are a core area of expertise for professionals knowledgeable in citizen science, particularly in light of the sensitive nature of environmental data under GDPR and other legal frameworks. It is essential to note that while these Citizen

Science Experts possess a deep understanding of regulations, citizen scientists may not always be familiar with these legal requirements. However, several challenges persist, including lack of standardized data formats, making interoperability across government, industry, and citizen science initiatives difficult. Access to official air quality data is often restricted due to proprietary formats and limited API availability, while commercial cloud dependencies raise concerns about long-term sustainability. Furthermore, poor documentation and metadata availability hinder effective data reuse. Key takeaways from the air quality workshop emphasized **the need for open-source infrastructure, harmonization of data, and robust privacy protocols**, with the Green Deal Data Space identified as a key strategy to improve interoperability and accessibility.

Water Monitoring Workshop: The water monitoring workshop participants excel in hydrology and water monitoring analysis, focusing on chemical and biological indicators such as pH, turbidity, and microplastics. Their expertise also includes field sampling techniques and permitting, ensuring safe and legally compliant data collection. Stakeholder collaboration is a key strength, as the workshop participants engage with local authorities, NGOs, and researchers to sustain monitoring projects. Additionally, environmental impact assessment and conservation play a vital role in translating data into advocacy and policy recommendations. However, water monitoring faces major barriers, including short project lifespans and funding gaps, which frequently prevent long-term impact. Logistical barriers in data collection arise due to restricted access to water bodies, requiring special permits. Many projects also struggle with validation dependence on individual experts, creating bottlenecks in data verification, and unclear data archiving and preservation management procedures and licensing standards, leading to inconsistent long-term accessibility. Insights from the water monitoring workshop highlighted that clear project goals and well-defined workflows can mitigate some challenges, while long-term solutions should focus on better training, standardized protocols, and sustainable funding models.

Biodiversity Workshop: The biodiversity workshop participants depict a reliance on ecological taxonomy and species identification by experts and volunteers engaged in species classification and long-term field data collection. The workshop participants also demonstrate strengths in metadata management and GIS integration, enabling spatial data handling and interoperability with platforms like OpenStreetMap. However, volunteer-based biodiversity projects face unique challenges, including retention and motivation issues, particularly among younger participants. Data validation and cross-referencing pose significant challenges due to taxonomic inconsistencies and a decreasing number of expert verifiers. It is important to note that some projects are now utilizing AI technologies to enhance the validation process, which may mitigate these difficulties. Additionally, long-term data sustainability is a concern, as biodiversity datasets require extensive curation but often lack funding, and fragmented data storage & interoperability limits cross-platform collaboration. The biodiversity workshop emphasized **the need for automation, clear workflows across data lifecycle stages, and strategies to enhance volunteer engagement through education, feedback, and inclusion in decision-making processes**.

4.5 COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

A cross-case synthesis of insights revealed five overarching challenge areas: **Data Quality and Standards, Technical Infrastructure, Sustainability, Social and Organizational Aspects, and Legal and Ethical Requirements**. These themes highlight shared obstacles across biodiversity, air quality, and water monitoring communities, underscoring the need for common strategies and systemic improvements. One of the key challenges identified is the lack of consistent data standards across organizations, which leads to interpretation problems and makes quality assurance more difficult. Without clear, standardized frameworks, the risk of errors, inconsistencies, and misinterpretations increases, impacting data reliability and cross-project collaboration. Several projects face limited access to key infrastructure resources, such as data platforms, storage solutions, and essential technologies. Additionally, the long-term maintenance and accessibility of these systems remain uncertain, often due to funding constraints. A lack of technical support further hampers scalability, reducing efficiency and the potential for expansion beyond pilot citizen science projects. A significant concern across all three use cases is the uncertainty of long-term funding and project ownership. Many initiatives struggle to secure sustained financial and institutional backing, making it difficult to ensure continuous development and impact. Without clear responsibility structures and long-term strategies, projects are at risk of stagnation or discontinuation. Motivating and retaining participants remains a key challenge. Low engagement levels and difficulties in coordination between stakeholders—including researchers, volunteers, and governmental bodies—lead to inefficiencies. The lack of structured support mechanisms at both individual and organizational levels further limits participation and long-term commitment. Uncertainties surrounding data laws, privacy regulations, and ethical considerations create significant barriers. A lack of clarity on legal frameworks for data storage and usage raises concerns about compliance, potentially jeopardizing projects and undermining trust among stakeholders. Addressing these uncertainties is essential to ensure legal security and ethical responsibility in data-driven initiatives.

Key differences between the three domains—Biodiversity, Air Quality, and Water Monitoring—based on the workshop results are:

1. Challenges and Frustrations

- **Biodiversity:** Focused heavily on engagement and sustainability issues, particularly how to keep volunteers motivated, integrate citizen science into education, and ensure data quality over time. Technical challenges included data validation, metadata management, and interoperability. It is important to note that Darwin Core and GBIF infrastructure could resolve these challenges, but might not been used by the workshop participants due to specific requirements that require customized data frameworks, which better align with the unique objectives and contexts of the projects.
- **Air Quality:** Faced major issues with data standardization, documentation, and privacy concerns. Unlike biodiversity, which had more volunteer engagement concerns, air quality focused on infrastructure, storage, and legal frameworks.
- **Water Monitoring:** Struggled with short project lifespans and funding limitations, making data quality and sustainability primary concerns. Validation was also a key challenge reported by the workshop participants, particularly in ensuring that environmental measurements were reliable over time.

2. Data Management

- **Biodiversity:** Struggled with multiple platforms, inconsistent metadata, and the need for cross-validation between different datasets.
- **Air Quality:** Focused on harmonizing data from various sources, improving metadata, and increasing the adoption of standardized protocols.
- **Water Monitoring:** Emphasized project-based data collection, where continuity and alignment across different projects were difficult.

3. Validation and Accuracy

- **Biodiversity:** The workshop participants reported that projects face weak validation processes, raising concerns over data reliability and consistency. While platforms like iNaturalist offer robust validation functionalities, the specific methodologies and dependencies of the specific projects the participants have experiences with may limit the implementation of similar validation measures.
- **Air Quality:** The projects of the workshop participants experienced gaps in validation, highlighting the need for automated validation and harmonization with official reference stations. These gaps may be attributed to challenges related to the calibration processes and the accessibility of official data, which hinder effective integration and validation.
- **Water Monitoring:** Struggled with over-reliance on a single validator, making it hard to ensure consistency.

4. Sustainability and Funding

- **Biodiversity:** Focused on long-term engagement of volunteers and infrastructure maintenance.
- **Air Quality:** Concerned with commercial cloud dependencies and the high costs of sustaining data storage.
- **Water:** Faced the most immediate funding constraints, making it difficult to maintain long-term projects and archives.

5. Solutions Proposed

- **Biodiversity:** Workshop participants suggested implementing AI validation and cross-validation among users to enhance data accuracy, similar to successful practices in established platforms like iNaturalist, eBird, and eButterfly. Additionally, while global repositories like GBIF already collect biodiversity data, smaller projects could benefit from adopting a similar approach to consolidate and share their data more effectively.
- **Air Quality:** The workshop participants' proposals include the development of open-source infrastructure, harmonized APIs, and standardized data formats (e.g., XML, JSON). However, it should be noted that standardized formats alone will not resolve interoperability issues. To effectively address these challenges, creating harmonized vocabularies and data structures that facilitate seamless integration across diverse datasets is necessary.
- **Water Monitoring:** Focused on improved training, guidelines, and automated validation tools.

Overall Takeaway

Within the group of the biodiversity workshop participants a major hurdle occurs with volunteer engagement - often regarding a sustainable long-term engagement. Air Quality faces technical and legal issues, particularly regarding data interoperability, privacy, and documentation. The workshop participants of the water workshop deal with short-lived projects, funding constraints, and inconsistent validation.

4.6 IMPLICATIONS FOR THE GREEN DEAL DATA SPACE AND PROPOSED SOLUTIONS

Interpreting the results in the context of the Green Deal Data Space, the findings highlight several obstacles and opportunities for solutions.

Table 13: Obstacles, Implications and Ideas for Solutions.

Obstacle	Description	Implications for the GDDS	Ideas for Solutions
Data Quality and Standards	The absence of consistent standards across organizations leads to missing or inconsistent data, making it challenging to compare, integrate, and assure the quality of citizen science data. Poor data quality can result in unreliable conclusions and hinder the effectiveness of research and decision-making processes.	Missing or inconsistent standards across organizations make citizen science data challenging to compare, integrate, and assure quality.	Promote definitions and data standards tailored for citizen science contexts, including metadata standards.
Interoperability	In the context of citizen science, interoperability is challenged by the lack of uniform data standards and vocabularies, which hinders seamless communication and integration of data generated from diverse sources.	Interoperability requires uniform vocabularies to enable seamless exchange, integration and analysis of data generated by diverse citizen science projects.	Establish vocabularies and validation protocols to enhance data quality and consistency.
Technical Infrastructure	Limited access to shared infrastructure, such as interoperable platforms, poses significant challenges for data collection and analysis. While organizations like GBIF provide valuable resources for biodiversity data, many citizen science projects still face barriers in utilizing these platforms effectively. Additionally, the absence of guaranteed long-term system maintenance raises concerns about the sustainability and reliability of the infrastructure. This can lead to fragmentation of data, inefficiencies in collaboration, and a lack of continuity	Interoperability hinges on robust, accessible platforms that support data exchange, processing, and storage for distributed citizen science initiatives.	Developing or recommending a scalable, modular digital infrastructure that supports data lifecycle processes (creation, sharing, validation) with open-access principles.

	in data management, ultimately undermining the potential impact of citizen science initiatives.		
Sustainability	Uncertainty around long-term financing and accountability for maintaining interoperability frameworks.	Without sustainable funding and governance models, the continuity of interoperability solutions is at risk.	Promote public-private partnerships and advocate for policies that secure funding for ongoing technical support and infrastructure maintenance.
Social and Organizational Aspects	Low motivation and commitment from participants can significantly hinder the success of citizen science projects. This challenge is often compounded by coordination issues, making it difficult to maintain active engagement among volunteers. Although numerous resources and materials exist that outline effective strategies for engaging and retaining citizen science participants, the implementation of these strategies can vary widely across projects.	Interoperability solutions require buy-in from diverse actors, including researchers, policymakers, and citizen scientists.	Facilitating co-design workshops can effectively engage stakeholders in the development of user-friendly and relevant interoperability solutions tailored to their specific needs. These workshops foster ownership of citizen scientists and empowerment, but also serve as educational platforms that enhance participants' understanding of interoperability challenges. To further support participant retention, it is essential to create an ongoing feedback loop post-workshop, where stakeholders can share their experiences and suggestions for improvement. By maintaining continuous engagement and addressing their evolving needs, the initiative can cultivate a committed community of participants invested in the project's success.
Legal and Ethical Requirements	Unclear legal frameworks regarding data ownership, licences, privacy, and ethical use hinder data sharing and collaboration.	Legal uncertainties can prevent the adoption of interoperable systems and undermine trust among stakeholders.	Creating ethical guidelines and licence templates for data sharing agreements, ensuring compliance with data protection regulations (GDPR) while fostering trust. While many resources exist for citizen science, they may not be easily accessible or well-publicized. To address this, a centralized repository or toolkit could be created, consolidating these resources and providing clear guidance on ethical data practices.

Within the workshops, participants co-created solutions based on the challenges they shared. The Green Deal Data Space should prioritize the development of ethical guidelines and licence templates for data-sharing agreements to ensure compliance with data protection regulations (GDPR), while fostering trust among participants. Additionally, it is important to consider the reuse and adaptation of existing guidelines, as there are numerous resources already available. By leveraging

these established frameworks, the Green Deal Data Space can streamline the process and enhance the credibility of data-sharing practices within the citizen science community. The insights gathered through citizen science involvement should be taken into account for further actions and follow-up projects. These perspectives reflect an understanding of the participants of the workshops on challenges and expectations. Citizen scientists should be recognized not only as data providers but also as active stakeholders in shaping the Green Deal Data Space. However, it is important to acknowledge that the consultation involved only a small group of individuals, which may not fully represent the diverse challenges faced by the broader community. To ensure a more comprehensive understanding, efforts should be made to engage a wider range of citizen scientists and communities, capturing a broader spectrum of insights and experiences.

Ensuring the long-term success of interoperability solutions requires addressing social and organizational challenges. Based on the workshops, the following recommendations for future actions can be stated:

- **Technical:** Develop modular, scalable platforms with clear data standards and validation tools
- **Social:** Use participatory approaches to ensure adoption and relevance of interoperability solutions
- **Sustainability:** Advocate for policy support and secure long-term funding
- **Ethical:** Define clear data-sharing agreements and legal frameworks

4.7 LESSONS LEARNED & REFLECTIONS

The workshops provided an initial overview of the Citizen Science aspects within the pilot case studies of the AD4GD project: biodiversity, air quality and water monitoring. During the sessions, participants realized that the challenges they face are not unique to their projects but are shared across different domains. Initially, they had perceived their issues as project-specific. Many participants highlighted the value of connecting with others and expressed a strong interest in more collaborative formats like these. From the workshop moderator's perspective, the biodiversity workshop fostered the most connection among the participants, likely due to its face-to-face format, which allowed for more direct interaction compared to the remote workshops as well as non-formal exchange beyond the workshop proceedings. Latter remotely based on logistical preferences for those particular use groups were organized. Interestingly, while one might assume that a face-to-face workshop would pose greater challenges, most of the difficulties encountered were organizational and primarily arose in the remote setting. Moderation in remote workshops proved to be more complex, as maintaining engagement, ensuring participants stayed on track, and keeping the activities structured required additional effort. Feedback collection methods also differed: for the face-to-face workshop, feedback was gathered immediately at the end of the session, while for the remote workshops, it was collected digitally and anonymously via email surveys afterward. Based on participant feedback, the face-to-face workshop was perceived as more successful. Moving forward, future activities should prioritize collaboration and knowledge sharing across different communities to enhance learning and synergy.

Based on the workshop series, insights gathered and feedback collected from the participants practical steps for collaboration between the workshop participants are joint data standards infrastructure, interdisciplinary training and capacity building as well as funding and policy synergies. To strengthen citizen science initiatives across various domains, it is crucial to establish joint data standards and infrastructure (He & Wu, 2020). This includes developing shared repositories for citizen science data, implementing common metadata schemas, vocabularies and APIs to improve interoperability, and promoting the use of open-source tools for data collection and validation. Additionally, interdisciplinary training and capacity-building efforts can enhance data quality and collaboration. A joint validator training program can equip volunteers with data validation and cleaning skills, while online exchange platforms can facilitate knowledge sharing among experts in biodiversity, air quality, and water research. Cross-disciplinary participation in conferences and workshops will further promote the exchange of best practices. Lastly, aligning funding efforts and policy strategies can enhance sustainability. By collaborating on funding proposals, creating policy recommendations based on integrated environmental datasets, and engaging policymakers, citizen science communities can ensure long-term impact and cross-domain synergy.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Studies presented in this report aimed to extract knowledge on data management practices, obtain views on FAIR and the GDDS initiative, and employ co-design activities to collaboratively identify key obstacles in citizen science data journey and collectively generate ideas on potential ways to address them.

Questionnaire-based study faced challenges in achieving the anticipated response target, with only 46 responses collected despite significant outreach efforts. This low response rate could be attributed to "survey fatigue," especially given the timing of this study, which followed a similar questionnaire published earlier. Stakeholder analysis is an essential part of every project, but the results of the existing studies should be repurposed as much as possible to reduce pressure on busy stakeholders, especially domain experts.

While diverse types of organisations and projects took part in the study, they shared common data management practices and challenges. Many projects employ custom-made tools and platforms to host their projects, collect and preserve data. While this affects data discoverability and interoperability, trying to create a monopoly where projects use common platforms and tools might neither be realistic in terms of infrastructure required nor appropriate for a variety of reasons. The reasons may include projects wanting to keep their identity and operate independently from larger initiatives, or institutions having own ethics and legal procedures of handling research data which prevents them from using external tools to collect and preserve data. Indeed, local initiatives aim to demonstrate their achievements and impact and create a sense of community – this also aligns with the notion of CARE principles to empower and acknowledge local people and their efforts.

On the other hand, if projects do not use standard approaches to collect, quality-control, preserve and document data, their data might not be considered valid or reliable to be applied in research, influence policies, affect decision-making by political entities.

Although many projects are willing to make their data more visible and interoperable by adhering to FAIR principles and contributing to initiatives like GDDS, the resources and support needed to achieve this are often insufficient. There is a clear need for greater resources for citizen science initiatives, both financial and technical, to support them in making their data more accessible and compliant with international or community standards. Additionally, initiatives like GDDS show promise in fostering greater collaboration and data sharing but must be designed to accommodate the constraints and needs of smaller, resource-limited projects.

The following recommendations can be made based on the questionnaire results:

- Ensure that FAIR principles are communicated in a more accessible way. Highlight that FAIR does not imply Open Data since this appears to be a common misconception.
- Endorse accessible toolkits for creating data management plans of varied complexity depending on the project's aims and resources available. Data management resources already exist and are available from major citizen science platforms such as EU-Citizen-Science⁴ and SciStarter⁵, but there is ever growing pool of materials making it difficult for the projects to find and select relevant resources. Standardised or community-endorsed resources are needed.
- Highlight the importance of publishing quality assurance protocols together with the data to increase data credibility.
- Emphasise the need for data licensing information, including obtaining data sharing consent from data contributors before conducting data gathering activities.
- Create and publish standardised vocabularies for describing data and provide guidelines on using standardised terms for data interoperability.
- Publish accessible guidelines on creating and publishing standardised metadata of varied complexity. Not many projects will have technical competency to offer metadata compliant to, e.g., ISO standards. Many projects are unsure what metadata standards are relevant, especially when collecting different types of data.
- Create domain-specific portals similar to GBIF that gather and harmonise citizen science data making it more discoverable and re-usable. GBIF is successful in defining a common data standard (Darwin Core Archive) and

⁴ <https://eu-citizen.science/>

⁵ <https://scistarter.org/>

offering tools for documenting data correctly before contributing it to the platform. Nonetheless, not all data collected by biodiversity projects fits GBIF and projects are left wondering where to publish additional data for re-use. This should be considered when building similar data integration infrastructures – what data is suitable for the portal and what to do with the data that does not fit but is still valuable?

- Data repositories and portals need to support continuous data streams and dataset updates (e.g., to correct errors) with data versioning and unique data identifiers.

It is also vital to remember that citizen science projects should not be treated solely as data collection apparatus. The core values of true citizen science projects lie in educating and engaging public in research, supporting and empowering communities, raising awareness and building knowledge.

The workshop series revealed key insights into the shared challenges and opportunities faced by citizen science projects across different domains. By fostering connection and collaboration, participants recognised that their issues were not isolated but rather part of a broader, common experience. The face-to-face format proved to be more successful in engaging participants and promoting non-formal exchanges, contrasting with the challenges posed by remote workshops, where maintaining engagement and organisation proved more complex.

Looking ahead, future activities should prioritise collaboration, knowledge sharing, and the establishment of joint data standards and infrastructure across disciplines. This includes the development of shared data repositories, open-source tools, and the promotion of interdisciplinary training to enhance the quality of citizen science efforts. Additionally, aligning funding and policy strategies will be crucial in ensuring the sustainability and long-term success of citizen science initiatives. Overall, a focus on cross-domain collaboration, practical steps for capacity building, and integrated policy actions will strengthen citizen science and foster lasting impact across diverse environmental research areas.

The co-design workshops can be seen as a kick-start to integrate citizen scientists' perspectives into the creation of a data space. Therefore, with the workshop series a first round of discussion was created. Taking into account the collected insights from the workshop series, it is recommended to keep the discussion going and involve those interested in sharing their experiences as citizen scientists to tackle data interoperability obstacles that occur when creating the Green Deal Data Space. Therefore, small citizen science communities as well as already international operating communities are relevant to involve in further co-creation activities to create a data network that works and is usable for local as well as international projects. This can be done by co-design creating solutions with the experts together. The aim with the further involvement should be to use the citizen scientists' expertise and experience knowledge to create an excellent user experience with the data space for a sustainable usage and success of the data space throughout different communities.

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7 ANNEX I: DATA MANAGEMENT PRACTICES SURVEY DOCUMENTS

This annex contains Participant Information Sheet, Consent Form, and the list of questions used for the questionnaire-based study conducted by Aston University.

All Data 4 Green Deal (AD4GD): Data Management Practices in Citizen Science Projects Survey

Participant Information Sheet

Invitation

We would like to invite you to take part in a research survey to investigate the current practices used by Citizen Science projects to collect, structure, document, store, and share their project data. In particular, we are interested in understanding the relevance of FAIR data principles* (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) for increasing visibility and reuse of Citizen Science data.

This survey is carried out by the European Horizon All Data 4 Green Deal (AD4GD) project (<https://ad4gd.eu/>) as part of a larger European Commission initiative to establish the common European Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) that will interconnect currently fragmented and dispersed data from various ecosystems, both for and from the private and public sectors. The GDDS will offer an interoperable, trusted IT environment for data processing, and a set of rules of legislative, administrative and contractual nature that determine the rights of access to and use of the data.

FAIR*, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Please note that all the answers will be anonymised and analysed in aggregations in order to ensure confidentiality of the data provided.

The survey should not take more than 25 minutes to complete.

Participant Information

Before you decide if you would like to participate, take time to read the following information carefully and, if you wish, discuss it with others such as your family, friends or colleagues.

Please ask a member of the research team, whose contact details can be found at the end of this Information Sheet, if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information before you make your decision.

What is the purpose of the study?

The survey is designed to:

- learn what tools, platforms and standards are currently used by the Citizen Science projects to collect, store and share project data;
- gather Citizen Science community views on the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) initiative; and
- understand projects' aims and ambitions and identify the perceived blockers to managing and sharing Citizen Science data.

Who is funding the research?

The study is being funded by All Data 4 Green Deal (AD4GD) Horizon Europe project. <https://ad4gd.eu/>

Why have I been invited?

You are invited to take part in this study because you have experience with Citizen Science project management or research.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you decide to participate, you will be invited to complete a questionnaire comprised of a set of questions regarding your experience with using different tools, platforms and standards in your Citizen Science projects, your practices of managing Citizen Science data, and your opinions on sharing project data via the Green Deal Data Space.

Do I have to take part?

No. It is up to you to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

If you do decide to participate, you will be asked to complete a consent form. You can withdraw from this study at any point in time by not submitting the questionnaire form. Your unsubmitted answers will not be saved. Once you submit the questionnaire form, you can no longer withdraw from this study.

Will my taking part in this study be kept confidential?

No personal data is collected in this survey. If you decide to provide your name and contact details for a follow up study, we will only use this information to contact you to arrange an online interview.

The data we collect will be stored within Aston University's cloud storage and only accessed on an encrypted password protected Aston University provided laptop.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Your input could help influence further research into tools, standards and guidelines to support Citizen Science projects in producing data compliant with FAIR data principles.

What are the possible risks and burdens of taking part?

Given the topic of discussion and the fact that no personal data will be collected, we feel there is minimal risk to you in participating.

In terms of burden, the survey will require approximately 25 minutes of your time.

What will happen to the results of the study?

The results of this study may be published in scientific journals and/or presented at conferences. If the results of the study are published, your identity will remain anonymous.

Who is organising this study and how is my data being used?

Aston University is organising this study and acting as the data controller for the study. Research data will be used only for the purposes of the study or related uses identified in this Information Sheet.

Who has reviewed the study?

This study was given a favourable ethical opinion by the College of Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Ethics Committee.

What if I have a concern about my participation in the study?

If you have any concerns about your participation in this study, please speak to the research team, and they will do their best to answer your questions. Contact details can be found at the end of this information sheet.

If the research team are unable to address your concerns or you wish to make a complaint about how the study is being conducted, you should contact the Aston University Research Integrity Office at research_governance@aston.ac.uk or via the University switchboard on +44 (0)121 204 3000.

Research Team

Victoria Lush, Aston University
Lucy Bastin, Aston University
Vitalii Kriukov, Aston University

Thank you for taking time to read this information sheet. If you have any questions regarding the study please don't hesitate to ask one of the research team.

All Data 4 Green Deal (AD4GD): Data Management Practices in Citizen Science Projects Survey

Consent Form

By completing and submitting this questionnaire,

	Yes	No
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time during the study by not submitting my responses.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I understand that I will not be able to withdraw my data after my responses are submitted.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I agree to my anonymised direct quotes from my responses to the survey being used in publications resulting from the study.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I agree to my anonymised data being used by research teams for future research.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I agree to take part in this study.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

AD4GD Questionnaire Survey

General Information about the Project

In this section, we want to collect some general information about your organisation and about your current or most recently completed citizen science project.

1. Which one(s) of the following best describe your organisation? *

- Government agency
- Local authority
- Not-for-profit organisation
- For-profit organisation
- Research institute
- Education sector (e.g., school, university)
- Citizen science project
- Other

2. Please provide the name and the website URL (if available) of your current or most recently completed citizen science project (the project you want to consider for this survey).

Project name: *

Project website URL:

3. Which topic areas does the project you specified above cover? *

- Space science
- Environmental science
- Health
- Social science
- Cultural heritage
- History
- Arts
- The science of citizen science
- Other (please specify):

If you would like to give more specific detail, please elaborate here:

4. Where is the project located? *

- Asia
- Africa
- North America
- South America
- Europe
- Antarctica
- Australia

5. If your project is based in a specific country or countries, please specify these:

6. Which geographic extent does the project cover? What is the geographic coverage of your participation level? *

- District
- City level
- Regional
- Country
- Multi-country
- Global
- Space-based project

7. What is the current status of this project? *

- Not yet started
- Active
- Periodically active
- On hold
- Completed
- Abandoned
- Other (please specify):

8. What is the planned duration of the project? *

- < 1 year
- 1-3 years
- > 3 years
- Ongoing (no planned end date)
- I do not know

Use of Tools in the Project Lifecycle

There is a large pool of platforms and tools that can support citizen science projects in managing project participation and/or collected data (e.g., CitSci, Anecdata, Zooniverse), data collection (e.g., Open Data Kit, iNaturalist), and data archiving (e.g., Zenodo).

In this section, we want to explore what standardised and/or custom platforms and tools you currently use or used in the past to run your citizen science project.

9. What platform do you use to host your citizen science project? *

- Custom built website or a webpage
- SciStarter
- CitSci 2.0
- Anecdata

- Zooniverse
- FieldScope
- iNaturalist
- GlobeObserver
- ArcGIS
- Social media
- Other (please specify):

10. What data collection tools do you use to collect the data from citizen scientists? *

- Sensors (e.g., fitbits, smart technologies)
- Paper-based datasheets
- Basic web-based datasheets (e.g., Google Forms)
- Custom built mobile application
- Custom built web page
- Open Data Kit (ODK)
- Epicollect
- CitSci 2.0
- Anecdota
- Zooniverse
- FieldScope
- iNaturalist
- GlobeObserver
- ArcGIS
- Other data collection tools (please specify):

11. What data storage facilities do you use to preserve the data collected by your project? *

- Local machine of a project member
- Remote server hosted by a project member
- Remote server hosted by a project member's institution
- Project member's institution repository
- Research library
- Public repository (e.g., Zenodo)
- Other (please specify):

12. If you use research libraries or public data repositories to preserve your project data, please list these below:

Data Collection and Data Management Practices

In this section, we want to find out about the data you collect and the data management practices you use in your project. We are interested in whether you use any standardised approaches to structuring, documenting, and sharing (if relevant) your project data.

13. What type(s) of data does your project collect? *

- Geolocation
- Observation
- Identification
- Classification or tagging
- Photography

- Audio recordings
- Video recordings
- Measurement
- Specimen/sample
- Sample analysis
- Annotation
- Transcription
- Other (please specify):

14. For what purpose(s) does your project collect the data? *

- Our own organisation's research
- Community building
- To support a local community to resolve an issue
- Environmental movement/action
- Policy making
- Local authority decision support
- Education / training
- Other (please specify):

15. Does your organisation have an explicit data management plan for citizen science projects (i.e., a document outlining the steps for preparing for data collection, data recording, data processing, data analysis, data sharing, and data storage)? *

- Yes
- No

16. If your data management plan is adopted from an external resource, what resource was used?

17. Is the data collected by the project quality-controlled? *

- Yes
- No

18. If 'yes', do you publish your quality control protocols?

- Yes
- No

19. Please provide a link to your quality control specifications, if these are published online:

20. Do you follow any formal approach to structure the data you collect? *

- Yes
- No

21. If 'yes', do you use international or community-approved standards to structure the data (e.g., WaterML, Darwin Core)?

- Yes
- No

22. If yes, please list the data standards that are being used:

23. Do you provide any information that describes and explains the data collected by your project (sometimes this is known as metadata)? *

- Yes
- No

24. If 'yes', do you follow any formal structured metadata standards (e.g., Dublin Core, ISO)?

- Yes
- No

25. If yes, please list the metadata standards that are being used:

26. Are there lists of standard terms that are used in your project? *

- Yes
- No

27. If 'yes', are these terms documented anywhere, e.g., domain-specific lists of terms, international or community-approved vocabularies (e.g., Environmental Thesaurus, EEA Air Quality Pollutants, ISO 6107:2021 Water quality Vocabulary)?

- Yes
- No

28. If yes, please specify where we can find these lists of terms used in your project:

29. Do you make the data collected by your project available for re-use? *

- Yes (directly after data acquisition/production)
- Yes (in a staged approach, i.e., after an embargo period or quality checking)
- No

30. Why did you take this decision?

31. Do you know the re-use conditions for the data you collect, including any licenses that apply (e.g., Creative Commons licences, Restricted Re-use)? *

- Yes
- No

32. If you publish your data and know the re-use conditions, do you provide 'data access and use conditions' statements together with your data?

- Yes
- No
- N/A

33. If you publish your data for re-use, what data publishing facilities do you use to share the project data outside of your project?

- Custom built project website
- iNaturalist
- GBIF
- Zenodo
- PANGEA
- Other (please specify):

Project Aspirations and Wider Outreach

In this section, we want to find out about your project goals and aspirations and understand what technical blockers still exist to run citizen science projects.

We also want to elicit your views on the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) guiding principles (described below) that focus on data interconnection and reuse outside of the initial purpose for which the data was collected.

34. Please briefly describe the main goals and aspirations of your citizen science project?

FAIR Guiding Principles

The ‘*FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship*’ are a set of guidelines that focus on machine capability to automatically Find, Access, Interoperate, and Reuse assets (including data). FAIR principles promote Open Data – data that is openly accessible, exploitable, editable, and shared by anyone for any purpose.

35. Were you aware of the FAIR guiding principles before participating in this survey?

- Yes
- No

Citizen science data can hold significant value outside of the project that collected the data. Reuse examples can include: combining the data with other data sources and visualising aggregated data on a map, complimenting air quality data collected by the official stations with citizen science data, using citizen science data for education and training.

36. How likely are you to make changes to your project management to produce data that aligns with FAIR and can be reused outside of your project? This includes adopting new tools, platforms and guidelines.

-

Very Unlikely

Unlikely

Unsure

Likely

Very Likely

37. Why would you take this decision?

38. What do you see as the main advantages to producing data that aligns with FAIR principles?

39. What do you see as the main blockers to producing data that aligns with FAIR principles?

Views on the Green Deal Data Space initiative

In this final section, we seek your opinion on the relevance and importance of the Green Deal Data Space initiative to citizen science projects.

The Green Deal Data Space

The European Commission is working on establishing the European Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) to interconnect currently fragmented data from public and private sectors. The GDDS will provide a trusted infrastructure for data processing and facilitate a set of rules to determine the rights of access to and use of the data.

Citizen science data can play an important role in complementing official data sources and is considered as a potential source of data for the GDDS.

40. Were you aware of the Green Deal Data Space initiative before participating in this survey?

- Yes
- No

41. Would you be willing to share your citizen science project data via the Green Deal Data Space (or a similar initiative, if your project is not located in Europe)?

- Yes (directly after data acquisition/production)
- Yes (in a staged approach, i.e. after an embargo period or quality checking)
- No (data cannot be shared externally)
- No (I do not see such initiative as relevant)
- I do not know
- Other (please specify):

42. What do you see as the major advantages of participating in the Green Deal Data Space or a similar data interconnection initiative by the citizen science community?

43. What do you see as the major barriers to participation in the Green Deal Data Space or a similar data interconnection initiative by the citizen science community?

Thank you for participating in this study!

If you would be happy to participate in a follow-up interview, please leave your name and e-mail address below. This information will not be further distributed, used as part of the analysis or made available with the survey results.

If you have any additional information to share with us, please feel free to use the text box below.

8 ANNEX II: WORKSHOP DOCUMENTS

This annex contains documents from citizen science workshops conducted by FIT.

Miro Board with Workshops Results of the Air Quality Workshop:

Miro Board with pictures of the workshop results of the biodiversity workshop including a digitized replica of the results on digital sticky notes for further analysis:

Miro Board with Workshop Results of the Water Workshop (in German):

Gruppen Teilnehmende:
 • Yannick
 • Julianne
 • Julia K.

Um den Prozess in Gang zu setzen, werden Daten aus verschiedenen Quellen gesammelt, z. B. aus Beobachtungen, Sensoren oder Berichten.

Die Daten werden überprüft und korrigiert, um sicherzustellen, dass sie korrekt sind und frei von Fehlern oder Unvollständigkeiten sind.

Die Qualität und Integrität der Daten wird bestätigt, um sicherzustellen, dass sie den erforderlichen Standards entsprechen.

Details zu den Daten, wie Herkunft, Struktur und Zweck, werden zum Nachvollziehen und Weiterarbeiten aufgeschrieben.

Die Daten werden sicher in einem Repository gespeichert, damit sie leicht zugänglich sind und erhalten bleiben.

Die Daten werden für Analysen, Forschungs- oder Entscheidungszwecke verwendet.

Die Daten werden verteilt oder mit anderen Beteiligten ausgetauscht, um die Zusammenarbeit zu fördern.

In dieser Phase wird sichergestellt, dass die Daten ständig aktualisiert werden, genau sind und im Laufe der Zeit für die laufende Nutzung zugänglich sind.

Daten werden neu analysiert oder für neue Erkenntnisse oder Anwendungen, die über die ursprüngliche Verwendung hinausgehen, wiederverwendet.

Die Daten werden langfristig und sicher gespeichert, so dass sie auch in Zukunft zugänglich bleiben.

Die Daten werden dauerhaft gelocht, wenn sie nicht mehr benötigt werden, so dass ein verantwortungsvolles Datenlebenszyklusmanagement gewährleistet ist.

Frustrationen und Schwierigkeiten

Wünsche und Bedürfnisse

Ideen für Lösungen

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Die wichtigste Erkenntnis in 1 Satz:

Limitationen durch proprietären, proprietären Datenformaten, Datenqualität, Interoperabilität	flexiblere und langfristige Finanzierung ermöglichen, Nachwechsförderer	Nachfrage & Integration der Daten, Integration der Daten, Integration der Daten, Integration der Daten
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Gruppen Teilnehmende:
 • Julia K.
 • Catherine
 • Benjamin
 • Malte

Um den Prozess in Gang zu setzen, werden Daten aus verschiedenen Quellen gesammelt, z. B. aus Beobachtungen, Sensoren oder Berichten.

Die Daten werden überprüft und korrigiert, um sicherzustellen, dass sie korrekt sind und frei von Fehlern oder Unvollständigkeiten sind.

Die Qualität und Integrität der Daten wird bestätigt, um sicherzustellen, dass sie den erforderlichen Standards entsprechen.

Details zu den Daten, wie Herkunft, Struktur und Zweck, werden zum Nachvollziehen und Weiterarbeiten aufgeschrieben.

Die Daten werden sicher in einem Repository gespeichert, damit sie leicht zugänglich sind und erhalten bleiben.

Die Daten werden für Analysen, Forschungs- oder Entscheidungszwecke verwendet.

Die Daten werden verteilt oder mit anderen Beteiligten ausgetauscht, um die Zusammenarbeit zu fördern.

In dieser Phase wird sichergestellt, dass die Daten ständig aktualisiert werden, genau sind und im Laufe der Zeit für die laufende Nutzung zugänglich sind.

Daten werden neu analysiert oder für neue Erkenntnisse oder Anwendungen, die über die ursprüngliche Verwendung hinausgehen, wiederverwendet.

Die Daten werden langfristig und sicher gespeichert, so dass sie auch in Zukunft zugänglich bleiben.

Die Daten werden dauerhaft gelocht, wenn sie nicht mehr benötigt werden, so dass ein verantwortungsvolles Datenlebenszyklusmanagement gewährleistet ist.

Frustrations and Difficulties

Wishes and Needs

Ideas for Solution

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Die wichtigste Erkenntnis in 1 Satz:

Aufgabenstellung ist klar und fest, Arbeitsaufwand für Datenbearbeitung	Der Datenzugang sollte mit dem Ziel der Integration zusammenpassen und die Zeit vorher klar definiert sein	Die Datenintegration, Integration der Daten, Integration der Daten, Integration der Daten
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Excel List with the results of all three workshops:

Use Case/Pilot	Journey (Phase)	Lane	Content	Group
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Quality assurance already necessary here	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Variables interpreted differently by different people	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Very intensive preparation of questionnaires or similar necessary to obtain data of sufficient quality	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Motivation of participants is difficult beyond "one participation"	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Support of participants for sufficient data quality is underestimated	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Access to waters, permits	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	Often hardly possible without contact to the person who collected the data	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	Correction must be well communicated with participants	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	You have to be careful that data is falsified	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	3: Validate	Frustrations and Difficulties	There is a lack of sufficient validation capacity, especially in the future	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	3: Validate	Frustrations and Difficulties	Example of biodiversity data: One validating person is often not enough	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	4: Document	Frustrations and Difficulties	only possible to a limited extent in small projects	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	Purposes with commercial benefit?	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	UI/UX	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	Platform is often unclear	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	possibly a lot of work if data has to be standardized or explained	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	Copyright, CC licenses	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	8: Maintain	Frustrations and Difficulties	Often outside the project timeframe - difficult to finance or no longer responsible	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	8: Maintain	Frustrations and Difficulties	Incompatible with project duration	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	8: Maintain	Frustrations and Difficulties	Financing costs for hosting and maintenance are often underestimated	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	8: Maintain	Frustrations and Difficulties	There is no long-term financing	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	8: Maintain	Frustrations and Difficulties	long-term responsibility -> who takes it on?	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	10: Archive	Frustrations and Difficulties	No standards yet established in the institution	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	10: Archive	Frustrations and Difficulties	Costs for hosting large amounts of data	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	11: Deletion	Frustrations and Difficulties	Data is not deleted	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	Summary	Frustrations and Difficulties	Limitations due to project duration; problematic to maintain data quality	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	More time capacity for preparing data collection	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	More personnel capacities	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	Longer project durations and stable funding	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	Better networking of projects	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Wishes and Needs	Enabling participants to "clean data"	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	3: Validate	Wishes and Needs	More support for young validators	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	4: Document	Wishes and Needs	Instructions for standards	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	5: Store	Wishes and Needs	see project means/term	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	5: Store	Wishes and Needs	Responsibilities must be clarified	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	Summary	Wishes and Needs	enable better and more long-term funding; promote young talent	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	Allow adequate time for preparation of data collection	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	Realistic project planning	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	Increase motivation through constant communication of results and benefits	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	Volunteer allowances	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	Networking of participants	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	Simple and streamlined data collection	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Ideas for Solution	Well thought-out data collection avoids extensive cleaning	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Ideas for Solution	Ensure contact with data collectors	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Ideas for Solution	Documentation of data changes	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	3: Validate	Ideas for Solution	Intensive training for data collectors	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	3: Validate	Ideas for Solution	Training on calibration and maintenance of sensors	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	Open, documented data interfaces	1
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	Summary	Ideas for Solution	Workshops & instructions for data collection (intensive support); think through data collection very well beforehand (scope, goal, methods)	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Many applications in use	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	While data is being collected, there is no ready-made concept for its use	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Costs/benefits of data collection not clear to everyone	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Choice of methods brings/causes different data distortions	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	The time lag between data collection and analysis can lead to frustration	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	Possibly subjective assessments - difficult to "correct"	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	Workload strongly dependent on the amount of data - sometimes difficult to estimate for Citizen Science projects	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	Different quality standards	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	Responsibilities for data verification/correction	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	Costs/benefits of data maintenance not clear for everyone	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	3: Validate	Frustrations and Difficulties	Participants may have to be contacted for explanations - Metadata	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	3: Validate	Frustrations and Difficulties	People who are familiar with standards may not be part of the project	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	3: Validate	Frustrations and Difficulties	Who or how can this step in the process be standardized for all data?	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	4: Document	Frustrations and Difficulties	Great effort, which does not necessarily contribute to achieving the goal within the project	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	4: Document	Frustrations and Difficulties	There is disagreement about the structure, e.g. keyword index	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	Costs for the cloud	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	Data protection? Especially when personal data is involved	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	Where can the data be stored sustainably and securely?	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	Licenses for data use and transfer. Who is the data originator?	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	Many different data qualities	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	Reliability of private data for decision-making purposes	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	Another data protection issue	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	Data is not always freely available to everyone	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	Time consuming	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	11: Deletion	Frustrations and Difficulties	Who defines such a point in time?	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	Summary	Frustrations and Difficulties	Distribution of tasks possibly unclear and high workload for data preparation	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	Clear concept at the start of the project (intended benefits, timetable)	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Wishes and Needs	Clarify and distribute responsibilities for data verification/correction	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	2: Clean	Wishes and Needs	Workflows must be clearly defined at the beginning (e.g. communication)	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	3: Validate	Wishes and Needs	Guideline for data standards in Citizen Science projects, for different data types	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	4: Document	Wishes and Needs	Mechanisms to validate the data by experts / other data sources	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	4: Document	Wishes and Needs	Adapt documentation effort to the service life of the data	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	5: Store	Wishes and Needs	Estimate the future use of the data	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	5: Store	Wishes and Needs	Official storage options, e.g. from authorities / analogous to the provision of other environmental data	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	6: Use	Wishes and Needs	Even if the data is not qualitatively sufficient for decision-making purposes, it can represent a preliminary stage and draw attention to issues	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	7: Share & Exchange	Wishes and Needs	Automated mechanism to share data with a defined Terms of use	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	Summary	Wishes and Needs	The data handling should match the goal of the project and the goal should be clearly defined beforehand	2
Pilot 1: Water Monitoring of Berlins lakes	Summary	Ideas for Solution	For concept development: Guidelines for standardization of different Citizen Science data types and for the (automated) validation of data	2
Pilot 3: Air Quality internationally	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Too many different data sources	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality internationally	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Different sources, not homogeneous	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality internationally	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Different data formats depending on the source	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality internationally	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Official reference station data is missing open API and easy access to be used and integrated.	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality internationally	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	too many different data sources	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality internationally	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	no standardized fill values	3

Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	different data formats	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	sometimes metadata is not available or accessible	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Closed APIs in different formats, closed sources, official stations are closed or maybe don't have API	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	I have a lot of problems with Teams, I don't know why I can't chat or activate my microphone. Only listen. And Mikro can't load in my cell phone	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	no documentation about checks	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	unclear if reference has uncertainties	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	the definition of the checks may not be clear or complete	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	Lack of comparison of the data with official stations, limited possibilities	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	4: Document	Frustrations and Difficulties	Outdated documentation	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	4: Document	Frustrations and Difficulties	Obsolete documentation platform, not user friendly	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	4: Document	Frustrations and Difficulties	documentation often incomplete	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	4: Document	Frustrations and Difficulties	No tools or guidelines to create metadata	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	4: Document	Frustrations and Difficulties	Probably more info complicate the load data	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	Data storage dimensioning	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	Choose best technology according to data requirements: volume, etc	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	sometimes access software (APIs) too complicated	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	poor performance of storages	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	Store format may benefit more some analysis than others	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	no common standards	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	site transferability?	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	Data from different providers is not interoperable	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	privacy terms	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	how we can engage stakeholders for using the data	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	8: Maintain	Frustrations and Difficulties	Institutions and government entities do not consider long term cost and dependencies of commercial cloud providers.	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	8: Maintain	Frustrations and Difficulties	resources not only to develop but to maintain the data systems	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	9: Reuse	Frustrations and Difficulties	metadata available for most air quality data.	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	10: Archive	Frustrations and Difficulties	archiving too much work and not intuitive	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	10: Archive	Frustrations and Difficulties	infrastructure not accessible to everyone	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	11: Deletion	Frustrations and Difficulties	EU funded projects and institutions lack a feedback loop once participants request the delete of their account and personal data.	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	11: Deletion	Frustrations and Difficulties	how does someone know when something is no longer needed?	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	11: Deletion	Frustrations and Difficulties	We never delete data	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	Summary	Frustrations and Difficulties	poor documentation, hardly any standardisation, no standard harmonisation	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	Select format in which to download data (XML, JSON, CSV, etc.)	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	ONE common source	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	Standardisation	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	Defined or standardized protocols, Open APIs	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	2: Clean	Wishes and Needs	more & better documentation	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	2: Validate	Wishes and Needs	improve and maintain testing	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	4: Document	Wishes and Needs	more documentation!	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	4: Document	Wishes and Needs	keep knowledge	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	5: Store	Wishes and Needs	adequate & performant infrastructure	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	6: Use	Wishes and Needs	implementation of standardized data structure	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	7: Share & Exchange	Wishes and Needs	a way to motivate them to use the data and show its importance	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	Summary	Wishes and Needs	more documentation, establish standards, provide performant infrastructure	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	Let it be. Communities do as best as they can.	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	Allowing initiatives to fail. Provide initiatives with opportunities.	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	Building layers of tools that allow to harmonise data.	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	Allow people to submit the results and let them be active, but allow communities to stay a closed community.	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	Display which data sets of national, regional and European institutions have which license and are reused where?	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	Provide an open API and challenge it by proving if it can be used by others without your involvement	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	8: Maintain	Ideas for Solution	Open Source infrastructure instead of commercial cloud solution	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	9: Reuse	Ideas for Solution	Enable reuse without your intervention even needed	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	10: Archive	Ideas for Solution	Provide everything ever measured as open data	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	11: Deletion	Ideas for Solution	Apply Privacy by Design principles	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	11: Deletion	Ideas for Solution	Provide the right to be forgotten. Delete all personal data on request and provide feedback once it's done	3
Pilot 3: Air Quality Internationally	Summary	Ideas for Solution	Green Deal Data Space!	3
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Unclear methods	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Lack of skills	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Lack of Budget	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Low Engagement	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Citizen Science as key element / subject at schools	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Indicators: "translation" - "methods" & Data Swamp	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Adapt Data for groups needs (e.g. childhood)	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	Important to have automatic tools to tag data that do not fulfill the minimum requirements	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	no clear data on species habitats to filter CitSci data on species occurrences	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	3: Validate	Frustrations and Difficulties	Not enough ideas how to validate habitat connectivity data by in-situ data (camera traps)?	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	3: Validate	Frustrations and Difficulties	In my work documentation is partly repeated, partly overlaps in different places (software description, paper, my own notes)	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	3: Validate	Frustrations and Difficulties	All tools	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	3: Validate	Frustrations and Difficulties	Possibility to allow volunteers to participate in this stage	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	No clear guidelines	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	Several servers, different protocols	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	Not enough tech experience with metadata handling (GIS, geography background)	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	policy global	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	Data with issues - if stored, occupy much more space	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	unclear data "language"	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	Standard access (different systems APIs)	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	No data sharing before paper publication	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	Publication on data journals? or Data citation index?	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	interoperability	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	8: Maintain	Frustrations and Difficulties	Who is going to maintain our workflows [code] after the end of the project?	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	8: Maintain	Frustrations and Difficulties	Reflected to store -> Permanent infrastructures (ORIG, ...)	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	9: Reuse	Frustrations and Difficulties	Uncertainty measures (thematic, spatial, temporal, ...)	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	9: Reuse	Frustrations and Difficulties	Harmonization (different data formats, thematic scope, resolution)	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	10: Archive	Frustrations and Difficulties	Citizen observatory as an infrastructure (long term)	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	11: Deletion	Frustrations and Difficulties	Data is always useful never delete it!	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	11: Deletion	Frustrations and Difficulties	How to address the problem when someone wants to finish his/her participation. Should we consider the observation as collective product? Particularly when other people has been involved (validation, ...)	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Frustrations and Difficulties	volunteers why they participate?	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Frustrations and Difficulties	interoperability of citSci data with other data sources	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Frustrations and Difficulties	data operational for policies and long-term research	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	Allow people to create their own projects with their particular interest	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	Communication officer to engage	4

Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	Not much citizen data on species occurrences in actual habitats (intact forests, e.g.]	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	Data at human scale, adapted to # groups needs: Data useful for vulnerable community & multidisciplinary team	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Wishes and Needs	Provide mechanism for collecting attributions (who has been involved) -> Licences	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	9: Reuse	Wishes and Needs	Not enough stakeholders to get examples of reuse (species of interest for habitat connectivity)	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	9: Reuse	Wishes and Needs	blockchain or similar: permanent identifiers	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	9: Reuse	Wishes and Needs	GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) compliance; privacy!	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	10: Archive	Wishes and Needs	Global repositories singleone? or multiple ones? key -> blockchain	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	Open Street Map data - to enrich land-use/land-cover data	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	2: Clean	Ideas for Solution	Keep intermediate outputs + potentially incorrect data with flags on issues (for example, "unknown habitat")	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Ideas for Solution	there is a developed workflow to calculate habitat connectivity. Not only Spanish case studies can be used, but everything (UK land use/land-cover)	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	License of code (tools, software) - open access includes commercial usage	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	More detailed data needed	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	Data license can be only non-commercial, depending on source	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	Zenodo (?) software: zenodo/GitHub	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	Data samples: GitHub	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Ideas for Solution	sustainable infrastructures	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Ideas for Solution	scalable and flexible processing	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Ideas for Solution	data on "human scale" / spatial and Temp. Resolution	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Ideas for Solution	community Manager	4
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	How to balance keeping data consistent vs adapting data collected for different group needs	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Training citizens should begin from childhood schools - it would facilitate future citizen science projects if every citizens 1st experience: was early on; besides, many could maintain their interest and contribution	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	Different time zones leads to incorrect times inputted -> and incorrect times taken from cam trap images	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	safeguarding -> deleting pictures of humans particularly children or indecent images	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	3: Validate	Frustrations and Difficulties	Big frustration! Channel of validation weak.	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	3: Validate	Frustrations and Difficulties	Is my data trash?	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	Storage: costs! warning with photo + video in particular	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	The more reliable is data less interested the owner is in sharing it	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	Aligning the decision makers goals with scientists and the general public. Many of them may be very disconnected from the scarce	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	What level of detail should be shared? e.g., location of protected specie / presence of humans	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	When using citizen science data for strictly scientific purposes, nothing is given back to the data collectors	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	Scientific: data should be made accessible to people from all backgrounds, focusing on people who have contributed to it	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	8: Maintain	Frustrations and Difficulties	Data from 2013 onwards -> Many changes on taxonomy -> need for a re-evaluation and re-classification of many obs	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Frustrations and Difficulties	Processing Data -> reliability	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Frustrations and Difficulties	sharing with citizens and aligning goals with decision makes	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Frustrations and Difficulties	technical issues	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	Formats (video, data coordinates feedback)	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	How to engage volunteers (more volunteers) and geographical distribution	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	2: Clean	Wishes and Needs	Different data sources -> different types of data -> joining everything together in order to use	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	4: Document	Wishes and Needs	Editing is not possible in strong systems steered to improve documentation	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Wishes and Needs	Selection of data useful and not	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Wishes and Needs	Access slow and default	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Wishes and Needs	see images one log one (boring)	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Wishes and Needs	Reliability low or zero	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Wishes and Needs	Format metadata wrong	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Wishes and Needs	where to share information to, particularly across countries	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	9: Reuse	Wishes and Needs	How to align the decision maker goals with scientists and society as a whole?	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	10: Archive	Wishes and Needs	Large storage carts of choice -> archive all data	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	11: Deletion	Wishes and Needs	when do we delete data?	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	11: Deletion	Wishes and Needs	what to do with partially incorrect data?	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	More education for volunteers	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Ideas for Solution	"Reusable" for volunteering in citizen science schemes - particularly for young people	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	2: Clean	Ideas for Solution	AI validation which increases citizen scientists engagement by: Filtering out human images, Filtering out blank images	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	3: Validate	Ideas for Solution	More experienced volunteers can be trained by experts in order to be more validators. This also provides an opportunity for people who want to dedicate more time to projects	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	5: Store	Ideas for Solution	Funding schemes that value: community engagement, sustainability	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	Match making of volunteers and projects	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	An easy to use database of common + unknown standards + protocols	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	Use common and known standards and protocols	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	Online groups or in person meetings between projects managers and volunteers to share data and real world results (like conservation policies)	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Ideas for Solution	technical issues: editing errors	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Ideas for Solution	money for storage, alterations, validation	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Ideas for Solution	AI: challenges in validation	5
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Apps with different fields that we need for the project	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Coordinates of the data collected by volunteer	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	don't be able to motivate people to do citizen science	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Frustrations and Difficulties	Money: consolidate a project that involves citizen science in a long-term perspective (currently difficult in the typical "4 years" scientific projects)	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	Integrate the FAIR principles and expertise as the barrier to clean the data -> Difficulties to adapt them automatic protocols	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	2: Clean	Frustrations and Difficulties	Time to validate the data with experts + robust sampling protocols to trust volunteers collected data	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	3: Validate	Frustrations and Difficulties	Aging of experts: gap in tech management	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	4: Document	Frustrations and Difficulties	Difficult to follow differences in taxonomy	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	4: Document	Frustrations and Difficulties	Translation of collected data into the formats we are working with	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	4: Document	Frustrations and Difficulties	Most laborious phase of the Data Life Cycle	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	4: Document	Frustrations and Difficulties	Camera trap videos: time consuming	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	Multiplication of platforms and apps -> Instead to improve previous developed than works	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	5: Store	Frustrations and Difficulties	Exploration of different standards to store and share: camera trap data: SIA plus, Camtrap DP	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	Rizpest challenge: to automate all these processes	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	Difficulties in interoperability	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	Decision of what standard to use to store the data to make it as interoperable and usable as possible	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Frustrations and Difficulties	Difficulties to meet the volunteers and policy-makers or decision-makers to share the data and took the actions (e.g. conservation planning)	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	with camera trap data: we've used sensor Things API + complex data; but very flexible and separation of concerns	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Frustrations and Difficulties	citizen generated data and "exchange": What citizens get?	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	8: Maintain	Frustrations and Difficulties	Who maintains the data when the project has finished?	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	9: Reuse	Frustrations and Difficulties	Do I allow companies to get money with my Citizen Science data?	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	10: Archive	Frustrations and Difficulties	Money hole	6

Pilot 2: Biodiversity	10: Archive	Frustrations and Difficulties	Legacy	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	11: Deletion	Frustrations and Difficulties	I always try not to delete data. I believe all data can be very valuable.	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Frustrations and Difficulties	walk towards collaborative-based citizen science when developing new projects to avoid redundancy	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Frustrations and Difficulties	Involving all citizen scientists in all Data Life Cycle	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Frustrations and Difficulties	Communication of knowledge generated by citizen science data	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	(for all phases) Money	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	1: Create & Collect	Wishes and Needs	robust sampling protocols adapted for citizen science	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	5: Store	Wishes and Needs	Communication of knowledge generator with the collected citizen Science data	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	5: Store	Wishes and Needs	connection of the new citizen science projects with already existing tools/projects	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Wishes and Needs	Include citizen scientists in all stages	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Wishes and Needs	Protocols to protect sensible species	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Wishes and Needs	Can we exchange protected data in a secure way?	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	3: Validate	Ideas for Solution	Cross Validation processes among different users	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	5: Store	Ideas for Solution	Money budget for infrastructures, for HR, for strategies of communication and policy making	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	6: Use	Ideas for Solution	Using already developed tools, experiences and projects to avoid waste of money and time	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	Bridge the gap between science and society to promote REAL conversation actions and no "diablabla"	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	More knowledge to automate the processes: share tools, share software, share workflow	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	communication management to volunteers (motivation, community sense) by professionals	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	create a platform to share frustrations and needs with other citizen science projects	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	7: Share & Exchange	Ideas for Solution	effort to share data even before publishing a paper	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	10: Archive	Ideas for Solution	Involve public admins in maintenance needs (infrastructures, money, human resources)	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	10: Archive	Ideas for Solution	create a "new vocabulary" in open science platforms to directly identify if an occurrence comes from a citizen science volunteer	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Ideas for Solution	Automatization of the processes in all phases of the Data Life Cycle	6
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Summary	Ideas for Solution	Budget to maintain the projects.	6

Graphic Recording (in German) of the Water Workshop shared with the participants in the post-communication:

INTEGRATION VON CITIZEN SCIENCE IM WASSERMONITORING VON BERLINER SEEN
21.11.2024
AD4GD

Malte Zanzow
FORSCHER BEI RWB & CITIZEN SCIENCE
DES WASSER-PROJEKTS BEI AD4GD

Leydi Benkers
FAIR EXPERT AT FRANKFURT INSTITUTE FOR APPLIED INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY (FIT) AD4GD

STAKEHOLDER WORKSHOP
INTEGRAZION VON CITIZEN SCIENCE IM WASSERMONITORING
AD4GD

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG
GRUPPE 1
GRUPPE 2

Graphic Recording Air Quality Workshop shared with the participants in the post-communication:

AIR QUALITY MONITORING WITH CITIZEN SCIENCE
 ADDRESSING KEY CHALLENGES FOR THE INTEGRATION OF CITIZEN SCIENCE DATA INTO THE GREEN DEAL DATA SPACE
 28.11.2025
 AD4GD

1 EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL DATA SPACE
 IT INTEGRATES CROSS-SECTORAL DATA TO SUPPORT THE GDD'S PRIORITIES LIKE CLIMATE, HEALTH, EURO POPULATION & SUSTAINABILITY
 KEY CHALLENGES
 COMBINATION OF DATA
 ENSURES DATA IS F.A.I.R.
 PROMOTES SEMANTIC INTEROPERABILITY
BENEFIT
 DIVERSIFIED DATA BRINGS ENVIRONMENTAL POLICIES
 D ENCOURAGES COLLABORATION ACROSS SECTORS
 D ALIGNS WITH THE EU'S STRATEGY FOR A SUSTAINABLE ECONOMY

USE CASE SOFIA (BULGARIA)
 THE PROJECT AIMS TO ADDRESS DATA GROUPS & IMPROVE THE ACCURACY OF AIR QUALITY MODELS
 high resolution mapping & data gap filling
 LOCAL SENSOR DATA CAN PROVIDE MORE ACCURATE AIR QUALITY INFORMATION THAN TRADITIONAL MODELS
 SENSOR DATA CAN ALSO BE USED FOR MODEL VALIDATION & GAP FILLING

Christian Berger
 EUROPEAN CENTER FOR MEDIUM WEATHER FORECASTS
 AD4GD

ILLUSTRATIONS BY JACQUELINE VILTMANN

1 DATA QUALITY
 Accuracy: REFLECTS HOW MUCH MODEL & CI ERROR-FREE
 Uniqueness: IT'S FREE FROM DUPLICATES OR REDUNDANCES
 Consistency: IT'S UNIFORM ACROSS SYSTEMS & FORMATS
 Completeness: ALL NECESSARY DATA IS PRESENT & VERIBLE
 Reliability: IT'S BASED ON TRUSTED SOURCES, RULES & STANDARDS
 IT SHOULD BE EASY TO VERIFY
 BUT THIS IS NOT ENOUGH - ESPECIALLY FOR THE FUTURE

2 FAIR PRINCIPLES
 "It's a guideline how to manage data"
 Fair: AVAILABLE WHEN IT'S EASILY ACCESSIBLE & IDENTIFIABLE
 Accessible: WHEN IT'S RELATED TO NETWORKS
 Interoperable: WHEN IT INTEGRATES SEAMLESSLY ACROSS PLATFORMS
 Reusable: WHEN IT CAN BE REAPPLIED FOR FUTURE APPLICATIONS
 "as open as possible, as closed as necessary"

3 IMPLEMENTING FAIR
 How to follow FAIR: THEY'RE FLEXIBLE, GUIDING DATA PRACTICES TO IMPROVE MANAGEMENT & INTEGRATION
 Technology of FAIR: BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF DATA, LINKS, APIs & SEMANTIC WEB LANGUAGES FOR INTEROPERABILITY
 Investment in FAIR: FAIR ADOPTION INVOLVES COSTS FOR TRAINING AND LIFETIME BUG FIXES, EFFICIENCY & INTEGRATION

4 IMPROVING RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT THROUGH FAIR PRINCIPLES
 Data Accessibility: ENABLES FASTER DELIVERY & SHARING OF DATA, BOOSTING META-ANALYSES & INNOVATION
 Reusability: IMPROVES MODEL REPRODUCIBILITY & TRANSPARENCY, ENHANCING TRUST AND TRANSPARENCY
 Infrastructure & Standards: PROMOTES STANDARDIZED AI, MODEL & FAIR-READY INFRASTRUCTURES FOR SEAMLESS INTEGRATION

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